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KRYSTALLE GENNISE C. AGUILAR

**CLICKSTREAM MOSAIC: A MIXED-METHODS STUDY OF PHOTO
DUMPING'S IMPACT ON LAGUNA COLLEGE STUDENTS'
COMMUNICATION, LIFESTYLE, AND SELF-DISCOVERY**

Thesis Adviser:

DR. RUTH B. RODRIGUEZ

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

30 July 2024

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Clickstream Mosaic: A Mixed Methods Study of Photo Dumping's Impact on Laguna College Students' Communication, Lifestyle, and Self-Discovery i

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Krystalle Gennise C. Aguilar | July 30, 2024

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This paper prepared by **KRYSTALLE GENNISE C. AGUILAR** with the title: **“CLICKSTREAM MOSAIC: A MIXED METHODS STUDY OF PHOTO DUMPING'S IMPACT ON LAGUNA COLLEGE STUDENTS' COMMUNICATION, LIFESTYLE, AND SELF-DISCOVERY”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

DR. RUTH B. RODRIGUEZ
Adviser

July 30, 2024
(Date)

DR. EMELY M. AMOLOZA
Program Chair

July 30, 2024
(Date)

DR. DIEGO S. MARANAN
Dean
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

30 July 2024
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Krystalle Gennise C. Aguilar, also known as Ktalle, Krys, or Talle by her family and friends, is a 22-year-old undergraduate student from Calamba, Laguna. She pursued a Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies degree at the University of the Philippines Open University. In 2020, she graduated with high honors in senior high school under the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strand at Colegio de San Juan de Letran Calamba. Her initial aspiration to become a doctor led her to shift her focus to her first choice, which is to pursue her creative endeavors at UPOU.

Throughout her college life, she is driven by her dedication to various causes such as mental health inclusivity, gender equality, community development, and promoting diverse art forms. She participated in several organizations like COPE UP and UP OPTICS at UP Diliman, as well as UPOU USC VolCorps and UP Siesta at UPOU. Infusing her passion for graphic design and photography, she leverages these skills to enhance the organizations' creative outputs and expand their outreach. Additionally, she contributes beyond her creative field by serving as one of the Event Organizers and Internals Committee members inside these organizations. Apart from her academic and organizational engagements, Krystalle also finds joy in exploring personality tests, ciphers, zodiac signs, cooking, nurturing her love for animals, and staning her favorite KPOP group, SEVENTEEN.

Wrapping up her journey in the BAMS program, she pursued her undergraduate thesis entitled *"Clickstream Mosaic: A Mixed Methods Study of Photo Dumping's Impact on Laguna College Students' Communication, Lifestyle, and Self-Discovery."* This study delves into the Photo/Video Dump trend, focusing on how it impacts the lifestyle and self-discovery of Instagram users, especially Filipino college students. Being a college student herself, she seeks to understand how these influences impact her peers, considering the challenges faced by many Filipino students when studying here in the country. Additionally, Krystalle aspires to pursue a creative career in production, continue her academic pursuits, and contribute to the welfare of stray animals in the community.

Acknowledgment

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To my inner child, connecting in your curiosity and eagerness to explore on a deeper level have been a significant inspiration for me during this study. Here's to embarking on more adventures together.

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DEFINITION OF TERMS

- **Engagement** - This term refers to a user's participation in online social media activities.
- **Clout Chasing** - This pertains to the influence or effort to attract attention in the online domain.
- **Screen Time** - This pertains to the duration that a user spends on a specific app, such as Instagram.
- **Content** - In this study, they are referred to as the photos and videos that were recorded or captured, and posted once the dump has been created.
- **Curate** - This pertains to arranging a collection of selected photos and videos in a way that aligns with the user's preferences.
- **Random** - This describes content shared online that seems out of context that is usually spontaneous, unexpected, and unrelated.
- **Unfiltered** - This term describes the unedited or raw version of a taken photo or video.
- **Self-portrayal** - This term relates to how one presents themselves online.
- **Track** - This pertains to observing or monitoring past actions, activities, and events that have been shared online.

I. INTRODUCTION

The popularity of photo/video dumps has captured the attention of many social media users, particularly during the peak of the pandemic wherein in-person interactions were limited or strictly prohibited in order to safeguard everyone's health and well-being. This mode of virtual engagement allowed individuals in the digital sphere to share their moments, memories, and experiences through a curated collection of photos and videos or a combination of both digital mediums. However, there's an existing debate whether this form of online interaction prioritizes an idealized perception of oneself to follow a trend or gain some public attention. Others argue that its essence lies in authentic and genuine sharing of personal experiences transparently and in an enjoyable manner. Notably, this trend has resonated notably with the Gen Z demographic, particularly among college students, including those in the Filipino college community. As these students navigate post-pandemic challenges with the return to face-to-face learning environments, they face a unique set of hurdles and adjustments.

The researcher's objective was to explore the influence of photo/video dumps on the lifestyle and self-discovery of college Instagram users, with a focus on students in Laguna, Philippines. Employing a Convergent Parallel design, combining both quantitative and qualitative research methods, the study aimed to comprehend user engagement, communication, and behavior related to photo/video dumps. A total of 100 eligible respondents were surveyed, and from these, 10 respondents were selected for Online Interview and Observation to delve deeper into the

research. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency distribution and percentages. Transcriptions were also made to further understand the data obtained from the Online Interview and Observation phase.

Research findings show that the majority of college Instagram users in Laguna dedicate 1-2 hours daily to the platform, or an estimated total of 14 hours per week. They occasionally take part in photo/video dumps by sharing and capturing random events. Meanwhile, CapCut is a commonly used app to create visually appealing photo and video compilations to add a personal touch. Interestingly, video dumps are favored over photo dumps. The engagement with photo/video dumps significantly influences the lifestyle and self-discovery journey of college Instagram users in Laguna, impacting various aspects like interaction, motivation, creativity, and authenticity. Challenges encountered in this activity include editing frustrations, privacy concerns, personal issues, among others, for which the researcher provides recommendations. While photo/video dumps may have started as a trend, they continue to serve their original purpose of personal reflection, memory preservation, and self-expression on a designated platform.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to understand how creating photo and video dumps affects the lifestyle of college students on Instagram, and how this type of engagement impacts their self-discovery. Furthermore, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. How active users are on Instagram based on the average screen time they spend on the application (commonly known as “app”) every week?
2. How often do they engage in posting dumps based on the frequency of their posts/stories on Instagram, the type of events/scenarios in the photos/videos taken, and the additional apps they use to produce the photo/video dump?
3. How do creating photo/video dumps affect their lifestyle and self-discovery based on the purpose of posting photo/video dumps, and level of validation and significance while engaging in the activity?

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to answer the research problem by undergoing several methods to gain an in-depth understanding of the study. Furthermore, the study aimed to:

1. Examine how college Instagram users in Laguna engage actively with the app by analyzing their screen time on Instagram;
2. Evaluate the level of engagement from college Instagram users in Laguna through the frequency of their posts and stories on the platform, determine the

nature of events or scenarios captured in their photo or video collections and identify the additional applications or methods utilized to create their photo or video content and;

3. Explore the impact of creating photo/video dumps on one's lifestyle and self-discovery, focusing on the primary intention behind sharing, and analyze the influence on lifestyle and the role in self-discovery during their engagement in the activity.

Significance of the Study

The study was a crucial exploration that delved into social media, its interactive nature, its ability to spark trends that engage people, and its personal importance to users. In particular, the study can offer benefits to the following:

Social media users. This study offers valuable insights for social media users, especially those who actively engage with trending topics and activities. While trends foster online engagement, it is essential to exercise discretion in sharing content, prioritize transparency, and demonstrate responsibility not only on Instagram but across all available social media platforms.

Filipino app developers. The qualitative data results obtained from this study offer valuable insights for application developers, particularly those operating within the Philippines. The research enhances comprehension of user requirements, particularly in the realm of photography and videography applications. It underscores the importance of striking a harmonious balance among creativity, adaptability, and time efficiency, as explained through comprehensive discussions with respondents during online interviews and observations.

Filipino college students. The findings of this study offer valuable insights into why the researcher selected this particular population for the study. Moreover, this research can resonate with individuals, showing empathy towards them in a positive manner.

Creatives. This research can inspire individuals, especially those in the creative field, where creativity plays a vital role in captivating social media users,

particularly those engaged in sharing photo/video dumps. The study aids in grasping the essence of this process, and how creativity sparks inspiration as individuals craft, enhance, curate, and distribute their memories to the online audience.

Future researchers. This study can prove beneficial for future researchers aiming to gain a comprehensive understanding of this concept or future concepts related to exploring various forms of interaction on social media. Such insights can hold significant relevance in users' personal lives.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study focused and were limited on the following: (1) Instagram was among the first platforms to introduce the concept of photo/video dumps, where users share a compilation of random photos and videos they have taken.; (2) Participating respondents are Instagram users for atleast one to two years; (3) Participating students are college students mostly under the Gen Z age group, known for their active participation in the activity; (4) There were a total of 100 respondents participating in the study; (5) the study was conducted in Laguna, Philippines, wherein various municipalities and cities in this province is essential as it encompasses both urban and rural areas. This diversity provides a broader and less biased range of perspectives from the population compared to heavily urbanized and highly developed regions.

The delimitation of the study were the following: (1) the age of participating respondents; (2) the gender of the participating respondents; (3) third-party apps used for producing photo/video dumps; (4) the result of the open-ended survey, interviews and the online observations.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Background

Social media has always been a widely used mode of communication in the online world. This platform offers various benefits when used effectively, enabling us to access information conveniently, connect with others, foster community, seek creative inspiration, boost businesses, stay informed about global events, and streamline work and academic tasks. During the pandemic, social media has played a crucial role in keeping us connected as many countries enforced strict lockdowns and regulations to prioritize public health. This shift in our daily routines has led to an increased reliance on social media. Several platforms were used for educational support, remote work setups, and bridging communication gaps when physical distancing was a necessity to ensure everyone's safety (Wong et al., 2020).

Amidst the challenges posed by the ongoing pandemic, a social media 'trend' that has emerged is the creation of photo and video "dumps." MacFarlane (2023) defines this trend as the curation of unfiltered visual content, including photos and videos, capturing memories, routines, and events to convey a narrative through online platforms. By offering a more intimate glimpse to personal experiences, it fosters connections among social media users, particularly in times of isolation (Gerrard, 2023).

A related phenomenon to this is "Romanticising Your Life" or "Main Character Energy," where individuals showcase select aspects of their lives to encourage others to appreciate life's simple joys. Particularly popular on platforms like

Instagram, this trend not only serves as a documentation of personal moments but also serves as a means of artistic self-expression in a refined and minimalist manner (New York Times, 2022). However, this mode of self-representation on social media has sparked debates regarding the authenticity of such portrayals. It leads to some questions about whether these expressions are truly authentic, if it merely contributes to an idealized self-image or if it is a trend that garners widespread participation.

The Body of the Review

Filipinos are recognized as among the most engaged social media users in Asia. They like online interaction and find pleasure in social media entertainment, communication, and following trends. The trend of photo/video dumps has captured the interest of many Filipinos, especially on platforms like TikTok and Instagram. This phenomenon has predominantly attracted Gen Z participants, whether they are following trends or simply sharing their content authentically.

Regarding this specific age group, college students in the Philippines exhibit unique characteristics in terms of progress, advancement, and convenience compared to their counterparts in other countries. College life in the Philippines has its common hurdles, such as passing courses, balancing academic commitments with other responsibilities, adhering to university schedules, aiming to complete required units each semester, and seeking effective coping strategies. While navigating through college is rewarding, managing these challenges presents a distinct set of obstacles for every student.

Instagram is recognized as a social media platform where users can share their photos and videos globally. The researcher selected this platform as the focal point for engaging in sharing photo and video compilations. Additionally, the researcher's goal was to connect with college students, specifically those who are active Instagram users participating in photo/video compilations amid the challenges of college life in the country.

The goal of this research was to investigate how photo/video dumps impact college Instagram users in the Philippines, specifically in Laguna. Through analyzing their platform usage behavior, engagement with photo/video dumps, and the influence of creating them on their lifestyle and self-discovery, the researcher aimed to gain a deeper understanding of this phenomenon.

Conceptual Framework

Social Media User Population and Instagram Usage in Asia and the Philippines

As the number of social media users around the world continues to increase, the Asia-Pacific region has taken the lead with over 2.9 billion users. The Eastern Asia region has over 1.2 billion social media users, followed by Southern Asia with 961 million users. Meanwhile, the Americas have an estimated 819 million online network users, and Europe has 681 million social media users (Dixon, 2023). In addition, the Philippines is the second highest country in Asia with the most social media users, following Timor-Leste.

According to the 2023 report on social media platform usage in Asia, Facebook remains the most popular, with over 960 million users (Kemp, 2023). Instagram follows closely behind with 780 million active users. In the Philippines, Instagram has the highest number of users after Facebook, with around 19.02 million users. Interestingly, there are 37.61% male users and 62.39% female users in the country (OOSGA, 2023).

Photo Dump: A Collection of Photos and Videos

A photo dump is a term used to describe a collection of photos and videos that are shared in bulk on popular social media platforms such as Instagram and TikTok (Demeku, 2023). Unlike a carefully curated collection of recorded events and memories, a photo dump often portrays a particular mood or story. It highlights a

random event that is related to a particular moment in the account owner's life, even if the collection of photos and videos are not necessarily related to each other.

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced people to stay indoors due to health concerns, which has resulted in strict limitations on in-person gatherings. As a result, social media has emerged as a valuable tool for connecting with others. Photo dumps have become a popular way for people to share glimpses of their lives and connect with others in the online space (Gerrard, 2023). These unfiltered collections of images don't require users to apply any presets or fancy photography techniques, making them more authentic and relatable. While some users may choose to apply a few filters or edits, the images are still far from being curated and produced. Additionally, a proposal authored by Jean (2022) highlighted that the engagement in this activity tends to be time-consuming, particularly during the curation process. The act of sharing dumps has emerged as a supplementary avenue for self-portrayal in the modern online realm. This practice allows individuals on social media platforms to exhibit their genuine selves in a manner consistent with their offline personas, as articulated by Schlosser (2019). In fact, the activity has become so popular that over 2.5 million users worldwide are actively engaging in it (MacFarlane, 2023).

Compiling photo dumps can be achieved through either carousel posts or video templates. Carousel posts are a single post that combines photos and videos, allowing viewers to swipe through the collection from right to left or vice versa. Typically, carousel posts feature four to ten photos and videos on Instagram (Herman et. al, 2020). Conversely, video templates serve the same purpose as carousel posts, but in video form, providing users with the option to create their own

transitions or select from video templates offered by applications and social media platforms.

Self-portrayal and Lifestyle in Instagram

Sharing personal content on Instagram is an opposed topic, with varying opinions on whether it accurately reflects the account owner's lifestyle and personality. Self-presentations are perceived differently by users; some consider those they follow to be either idealistic or authentic. In reality, self-portrayal often varies based on the account users themselves. Research has shown that Instagram users tend to post content that creates an idealized, socially desirable impression, or reflects a positive personality to impress followers. Unfortunately, such behaviour often results in negative outcomes (Blackwell, 2017). The idea was discussed in detail in the article by Fan et al. (2019), emphasizing how these posts could establish unattainable benchmarks for audiences, leading to a potential to lower their mood and self-esteem.

However, other studies suggest that some users employ Instagram as a tool to show their real selves, with content that is more relatable, honest and positively received by others (Harris and Bardey, 2019). This has encouraged more users to post inclusive and genuine content, thereby allowing Instagram to become a self-presentational tool in both the online and offline world.

By engaging in reflective activities, users can reduce negative feelings and clear their minds of draining thoughts. This practice also promotes awareness and

encourages individuals to slow down, which is especially important in today's fast-paced world. Reflecting also helps users keep track of their daily activities, including seemingly insignificant ones like taking a walk, watering plants, or writing in a journal. It's worth noting that some individuals leverage it as a gratitude exercise (Vicenty, 2022).

III. METHODOLOGY

This section provided information on the methods that were used in this study. It includes the research design, research locale, respondents of the study, data gathering procedure, and data analysis plan.

Research Design

This study focused on mixed methods research, particularly the Convergent Parallel Design. This study intended to identify social engagement and behavior on Instagram, explored what type of events do college students record, what methods do they use when producing photo/video dumps and explored how photo/video dumps affect their self-discovery and lifestyle.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The study focused and were limited on the following: (1) Instagram was among the first platforms to introduce the concept of photo/video dumps, where users share a compilation of random photos and videos they have taken.; (2) Participating respondents are Instagram users for atleast one to two years; (3) Participating students are college students mostly under the Gen Z age group, known for their active participation in the activity; (4) There were a total of 100 respondents participating in the study; (5) the study was conducted in Laguna,

Philippines, wherein various municipalities and cities in this province is essential as it encompasses both urban and rural areas. This diversity provides a broader and less biased range of perspectives from the population compared to heavily urbanized and highly developed regions.

The delimitation of the study were the following: (1) the age of participating respondents; (2) the gender of the participating respondents; (3) third-party apps used for producing photo/video dumps; (4) the result of the open-ended survey, interviews and the online observations.

Respondents of the Study

The researcher identified Instagram users' social engagement and behavior, as well as the content and methods of producing photo/video dumps, and explored how photo/video dumps affect their lifestyle and self-discovery. To sustain and observe unbiasedness, college students residing in Laguna were asked to participate. There were a total of 100 respondents with 9.8% margin of error and 95% confidence level.

Sampling Method

The researcher employed the Convergent Parallel Design, merging quantitative and qualitative methods for analysis. Two sampling techniques were utilized to meet the sampling requirements.

For the quantitative analysis, the cluster sampling method was applied to address dispersed populations in the chosen research area, Laguna. This was crucial as the province remains one of the largest provinces in CALABARZON, ensuring that respondents still meet the specified qualifications.

Conversely, the purposive sampling method was used for the qualitative analysis. At least 10 respondents participated in individual interviews and observations selected from 100 survey participants.

Data Gathering Procedures

An open-ended survey, interviews, and online observation were conducted and were mainly used in attaining data collection.

By combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, an open-ended survey was carried out to explore the social media engagement and behavior of college Instagram users. It focused on their frequency of posting photo/video dumps and how this type of activity influences lifestyle, and self-discovery. To gain a more thorough understanding of the study, chosen participants were subject to both individual interviews and observations. This is to track their usage of third-party apps to edit their photos and videos, as well as the other types of media they utilize. All activities were executed with the explicit consent of the participants.

In general, 100 responses were collected for the survey. From there, a minimum of 10 respondents were selected to participate in individual interviews and observations depending on their willingness to participate in the additional activity.

Both descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis were employed to analyze the data collected.

Research Instrument

The researcher gathered information through conducting an open-ended survey, and online interviews and observations. The presentation in the research problem served as a reference for both data gathering procedures. The instruments (see Annex A) that were used are the following:

- Google Forms for conducting the open-ended survey
- Canva to design a publicity survey invitation poster.
- Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Discord, and X (previously known as Twitter) to reach a broader audience.
- Certification Document from TCPS 2: Course on Research Ethics, to fulfill the research ethics prerequisite before starting interviews and observations.
- A cover letter and consent form written by the researcher and approved by the chosen respondents for the online observation.
- Zoom or Google Meet and;
- Google Drive and Google Sheets for the safekeeping of the data gathered for the study.

Data Analysis

Data that was gathered from the survey was presented for interpretation through Google Forms. Data was encoded into Google Sheets.

For open-ended questions, the responses were typed out and then categorized in terms of similarity in the essence of the response. To summarize the data, frequency count and percentages are used to obtain a valid and reliable interpretation.

Frequency distribution (count). Data collected are calculated and arranged according to category/categories for each required information.

Percentages. The frequencies are converted into percentages to visualize the results or information derived from the distribution easily.

Table 1. Statistical Treatment for each Research Problem.

RESEARCH PROBLEM	SOURCES	STATISTICAL TREATMENT
How active users are on Instagram based on the average screen time they spend on the app every week?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Frequency Distribution• Percentages

How often do they engage in posting dumps based on the frequency of their posts/stories on instagram, the type of events/scenarios in the photos/videos taken, and the additional apps they use to produce the photo/video dump?

- Survey

- Frequency Distribution
- Percentages

- Online Observation

-not applicable-

How do creating photo/video dumps affect their lifestyle and self-discovery based on the purpose of posting photo/video dumps, and level of validation and significance while engaging in the activity?

- Online Interview

-not applicable-

Ethical Consideration

To ensure the safety of the participants' involvement, the researcher has completed the *TCPS 2: Course on Research Ethics* (see Annex A, Page 103). This course aimed to meet the research ethics requirement before commencing activities that required human participation in this study.

The participation of the respondents especially in the Online Interview and Observation phase will remain anonymous, as written in the introduction of the survey, cover letter, and consent form prepared by the researcher.

Study Procedure Schedule

This table acted as a roadmap for the proposed study's activities, in accordance with the academic year's formal calendar before its alteration. The timeline was subjected to revision based on the approval of the research proposal, which was approved in the first stage of the study during the 1st Trimester, A.Y. 2023 - 2024.

While minor adjustments were made such as extending the Analysis of Results stage, the researcher aimed to adhere to the original schedule despite the alterations in the Academic Calendar.

Table 2. Timeline of the Study's Procedure.

Activities	Dates
Capsules Presentation	October 30, 2023
Proposal Writing	November 20 - December 1, 2023
Revision of Proposal	December 4 - 8, 2023
Presenting of Proposal for MMS 199	December 13, 2023
Approval of Research Proposal	December 18, 2023
Revision of Overall Approved Research Proposal	January 6, 2023 - February 12, 2024
Preparation for conducting and revising Research Methodology	February 13 - March 13, 2024
Distribution of Survey & Selection of Respondents for Online Interviews and Observation	March 14 - April 14, 2024
Preparation for Information Gathering of Selected Respondents for Online Interviews and Observation	April 14 - 20, 2024
Online Interviews and Observation of Selected Respondents	April 21 - May 12, 2024

Refining of Overall Paper and Creating Backups for Collected Data	May 12 - 25, 2024
Analysis of Results	June 1 -15, 2024
Writing of Discussion of Results	June 16 - July 20, 2024
Thesis Submission and Approval	July 21 - August 17, 2023

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter outlined the findings, interpretation, and analysis of the collected data of the study. The objective of the results and discussion was to address the questions related to the research problem through (1) identifying the social engagement and behavior of Instagram users, (2) exploring what type of events do college students record based on the content of their dumps, what methods do they use when producing photo/video dumps, and (3) exploring how photo/video dumps affect their self-discovery and lifestyle.

The researcher successfully collected 100 responses through Google Forms to investigate the social media interactions and habits of college students on Instagram. The estimated population of Laguna is approximately 3,382,193 according to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2021). The margin of error in the results is around 9.8% with a sample size of 100 college respondents from Laguna. The study also focused on their posting frequency of photo/video dumps and how this activity influences their lifestyle and self-discovery. Additionally, 10 respondents agreed to participate in the next stage of the research, which involved the Online Interviews and Observations. During this phase, participants were given the option to begin with interviews discussing the effects of photo/video dumps on college Instagram users or engage in observations that include authorized sharing of dump creation photos or videos.

The interview focused on participants' experiences with exploring photo and video collections. It includes their preferences for capturing photos or videos, methods of engagement, opinions on using additional apps, and the influence of the

activity on their lifestyle, and self-discovery. The quantity of interview questions was based on their survey responses, with a maximum of only six questions.

Throughout the online observation, the researcher asked participants to demonstrate their method of creating photo/video dumps through screen sharing. This engagement provided the researcher with valuable insights into the participants' thinking patterns, organizational abilities, and creativity in curating photo or video compilations. Participants were given the choice to either create a collection in real-time or present an existing workspace while describing their curation process before sharing it. This method ultimately encouraged a deeper and more insightful examination of the participants' strategies and the motivations influencing their curation process.

To enhance the safety of the participants' involvement, the researcher has completed the ***TCPS 2: Course on Research Ethics*** to meet the research ethics requirement before commencing interviews and observations.

Phase One: Survey Results

Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 3. Age of the Respondents.

Age		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
18 - 20	39	39%
21 - 25	57	57%
26 - 35	4	4%
TOTAL	100	100%

The largest segment of participants falls within the 21-25 age bracket, with 57 respondents, closely followed by individuals aged 18-20, with 39 respondents. Additionally, there are 4 participants in the 26-35 age categories, with the eldest respondent being 35 years old.

Table 4. Preferred Gender Pronouns of the Respondents.

Gender Pronouns		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
He/Him	33	33%
She/Her	63	63%
They/Them	0	0%
Prefer not to say	3	3%
Other Gender Pronouns Indicated by the Respondent		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
She/They	1	1%
TOTAL	100	100%

The researcher aimed to promote gender inclusivity in the survey by opting to inquire about the preferred gender pronouns of respondents instead of their sex. An option for 'others' was included to accommodate any additional gender pronouns preferred by the respondents.

The survey results indicate that 63 respondents prefer using the pronouns She/Her, followed by 33 respondents who indicated a preference for He/Him. Additionally, one respondent specified using the pronouns She/They. Three

respondents chose not to disclose their gender pronouns, whereas none of the respondents identified with the pronouns They/Them.

Table 5. College Year Standing of the Respondents.

College Year Standing		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
First Year (I)	17	17%
Second Year (II)	31	31%
Third Year (III)	9	9%
Fourth Year (IV)	39	39%
Fifth Year (V)	4	4%
TOTAL	100	100%

The majority of respondents are presently in their fourth year of college, with 39 participants. Following this group are second-year college students, totaling 31 respondents. Seventeen participants are in their first year of college, while 9 respondents are in their third year. The remaining 4 respondents are in their fifth year of college.

Table 6. College Course or Program of the Respondents.

College Course / Program		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor of Science Courses	72	72%
Medicine Courses	11	11%
Bachelor of Arts Courses	11	11%
Education Courses	4	4%
HRM Courses	1	1%
Public Administration Courses	1	1%
TOTAL	100	100%

The majority of respondents, totaling 72, are currently enrolled in Bachelor of Sciences courses. Among them, BS Architecture students make up the biggest number with 9% of the total population. On the other hand, both Medicine Courses and Bachelor of Arts courses have an equal number of 11 respondents each. The highest number of respondents in the Medicine courses are from Dental Medicine and Doctor of Medicine, each accounting for 5% of the respondents. Additionally, 7% of the respondents are pursuing Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies, making them the largest group among Bachelor of Arts Courses. The rest of the respondents

include 4 from Education Courses, and 1 of each from HRM Course and Public Administration Courses.

Table 7. Respondents' Residency in Laguna.

Location in Laguna		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Calamba	37	37%
Los Baños	8	8%
Cabuyao	12	12%
Biñan	5	5%
San Pedro	7	7%
Calauan	2	2%
Sta Rosa	5	5%
Sta Cruz	6	6%
Pagsanjan	2	2%
Bay	1	1%
Pangil	7	7%
Siniloan	4	4%

Famy	1	1%
Paete	1	1%
San Pablo	2	2%
TOTAL	100	100%

Majority of the respondents are residing in Calamba Laguna with a total of 37 respondents, followed by 12 respondents residing in Cabuyao, 8 respondents from Los Baños, 7 respondents each from Pangil and San Pedro, and the remaining 29 respondents came from different cities and municipalities around Laguna.

Instagram Usage and Engagement in Photo / Video Dumps

Table 8. Respondents' Screen Time on Instagram per day.

Time Spent on Instagram (per day)		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
10 - 29 minutes	19	19%
30 - 59 minutes	29	29%
1 hour - 2 hours	44	44%
2 hours - 59 minutes	3	3%
3 - 5 hours	5	5%
TOTAL	100	100%

On average, respondents typically dedicate 35 hours per week on Instagram, translating to approximately 5 hours maximum daily. While the majority, comprising 44 respondents, spend 1 to 2 hours daily on the platform with a total of 14 hours per week. Following this group, 29 respondents use Instagram for 30 to 59 minutes daily. A smaller proportion, consisting of 19 respondents, use Instagram for 10 to 29 minutes daily. Additionally, 3 respondents allocate 2 hours to 59 minutes daily, and 5 respondents report the highest usage, spending 3 to 5 hours daily on Instagram.

Table 9. Respondents' Active Engagement on Instagram.

Engagement in Photo / Video Dumps		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
Always	7	7%
Very Frequently	15	15%
Occasionally	52	52%
Rarely	19	19%
Very Rarely	7	7%
Never	0	0%
TOTAL	100	100%

When considering the active involvement of college Instagram users, a majority of respondents, totaling 52, disclosed engaging in photo/video dumps Occasionally. Following this are 19 respondents indicating rare participation, while 15 respondents stated very frequent engagement in this activity. Similarly, an equal number of 7 respondents expressed their engagement as always and very rarely based on their active involvement.

Notably, none of the respondents selected 'never' as their level of participation in this activity.

Figure 1. Content Collected for Photo/Video Dumps.

Content Being Collected and Posted

Table 10. Content Collected for Photo/Video Dumps.

Content Being Collected and Posted	
Gathering	50 (50%)
Daily Routine	29 (29%)
Random Events	76 (76%)
Special Events	69 (69%)
Self-expression	51 (51%)
Other Content Indicated by the Respondents	
Dog, food, scenery	1 (1%)

Travels	2 (2%)
Film Reviews	1 (1%)
Memes	1 (1%)
Spiritual Growth	1 (1%)
Art	1 (1%)

To help the respondents in identifying common types of content in their photo/video collections, the researcher presented five typical categories found in photo or video dumps, while allowing respondents to add any additional content they typically include in their collections. The data illustrates that a significant number of respondents, totaling 76, incorporate Random Events in their collections. Following this, 69 respondents indicated that they included Special Events, while Self-expression, Gathering, and Daily Routine were included by 51, 50, and 29 respondents, respectively.

Moreover, respondents mentioned other content, with 1 respondent including Dog, Food, and Scenery in their collections. Travels was also included by 2 respondents, while individual respondents mentioned Film Review, Memes, Spiritual Growth, and Art in their collections.

Table 11. Utilization of Other Applications.

Utilization of Other Applications		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
YES	77	77%
NO	23	23%
TOTAL	100	100%

When asked about using other applications during the editing and curation process of their photo/video collections, most of the respondents, a total of 77, acknowledged using additional apps. On the other hand, 23 respondents stated that they do not use any extra applications in their process.

Figure 2. Applications Utilized by the Respondents.

Applications Being Utilized

Table 12. Applications Utilized by the Respondents.

Applications Being Utilized	
Instagram	55 (65.5%)
TikTok	42 (50%)
CapCut	77 (64.3%)
Adobe Creative Suite	19 (19%)
Other Applications Indicated by the Respondents	
Snapseed	2 (2.4%)
Made, SCRL, Procreate Pocket	1 (1.2%)
Picsart	1 (1.2%)
Canva	2 (2.4%)
YouCut	1 (1.2%)
VSCO	1 (1.2%)

For respondents who answered YES in the previous question, the researcher asked about the additional applications they utilize before sharing their photo/video content. The data indicates that an equal number of 77 respondents, rely on CapCut as their primary editing tool, enabling them to edit both photos and videos within a single platform. Following closely, Instagram is utilized by 55 respondents for its basic editing features catering to both photo and video content. Moreover, 42

respondents incorporate TikTok into their editing process, while 19 respondents opt for the Adobe Creative Suite for editing their multimedia content.

Furthermore, respondents mentioned additional editing tools like Made, SCRL, and Procreate Pocket, recommended by 1 respondent, alongside Picsart, YouCut, and VSCO each mentioned by 1 respondent. Interestingly, 2 respondents acknowledged using Canva for their editing needs.

Photo and Video Dumps: Their Impact on Lifestyle and Self-discovery

PRIMARY REASONS OF ACTIVELY ENGAGING TO PHOTO/VIDEO DUMPS

Upon inquiring about the primary motivations behind their involvement in creating, sharing, and engaging in photo/video dumps, the majority of the responses can be categorized as follows:

Archiving Old Photo and Video Collections

One significant factor motivating respondents to partake in photo/video dumps is the opportunity it presents to effectively archive their photo and video collections. By documenting, compiling, curating, and sharing their collections on Instagram, individuals can conveniently reduce the heavy storage on their devices while creatively preserving memorable moments.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“Either to share or just to post pictures to be disposed from the gallery”*
- *“For storing memories and archiving”*
- *“So that I can save up the memories of that day into one collective video/post. Also use insta as a gallery dump to free up space in my phone camera roll.”*

Sharing Events in Life

Similar to the common practice observed among social media users across various platforms, college Instagram users frequently engage in sharing personal experiences from both academic and non-academic realms. This activity not only

serves as a means to update their peers about ongoing events in their lives but also allows them to reminisce about shared moments with those in their social circle.

Moreover, some respondents have acknowledged that despite sharing memories publicly, they are selective in including only those individuals they have chosen to follow on Instagram to maintain a level of privacy and control over their audience.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“One of my primary reasons is to share something about my life or one of my goals that I have achieved in my life.”*
- *“To store and capture the current memories right in front of me. It acts as a reminder and at the same time, a proof that I am living my life.”*
- *“Proof of life 😊 kidding aside. I sometimes feel it’s worth sharing, especially those inspirational quotes and illustrations. Also, sharing some photos or videos that made me happy. With that, it feels like I’m sharing my happiness with friends/relatives who find it also worth the engagement.”*

Clout Chasing

Clout chasing refers to leveraging social media to increase visibility through participation in current trends, often fueled by a desire for social connection, attention, and keeping up with the trend. While photo/video dumps initially gained popularity as a trend, clout chasing has emerged as a predominant incentive for some respondents.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“For Updates, for da clout”*
- *“Trend really have power over us and to me kahit diko trip, pag may nakita ako na maganda style, like sa pananamit, in the following days gagayahin ko din subconsciously”.*

To Interact with Others

Engagement in photo/video sharing dumps fosters interaction among the respondents. This aspect stands out as a key tool of engagement, particularly with the introduction of Instagram's 'Add Yours' feature. This functionality enables users to connect with others who share similar interests, creating a community of like-minded individuals that encourages sharing.

In addition to fostering engagement, the research highlighted how this activity facilitates connections or reconnections with followers. By providing updates on their lives and staying informed about others, even those separated by distance, participants experience a sense of belonging. Witnessing mutual followers' experiences and knowing that their own content is appreciated contributes to this sense of connection. One notable insight gathered from respondents is their motivation to get the attention from someone special among their followers.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“Updating my friends/followers & connecting with them”*
- *“I engage with sharing photos and videos (dumps) online because it is one way for me to interact with my friends and family.”*

Self Expression and Creativity

Photo and video dumps have evolved into platforms enabling participants to articulate themselves through curated visual collections. For individuals facing challenges in conveying themselves physically or verbally, this exercise serves as a valuable outlet for self-expression, particularly benefiting those whose creativity serves as their primary mode of communication.

Some respondents aspire to explore their creativity as a form of self-expression. They acknowledge that engaging in creativity allows them to freely express themselves. In particular, individuals passionate about photography and videography often channel this enthusiasm into their visual collections, effectively intertwining self-expression with their artistic endeavors.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I share memorable experiences, and having photo/video dumps help me express myself freely. I am also passionate in photo and video editing and I use my own experience as an example.”*
- *“For self aesthetic, to express my mood/feelings”*
- *“Self expression and so it’s more convenient to look back on life events and such”*

Self Enjoyment and Satisfaction

The majority of respondents acknowledged their enjoyment in participating in photo/video dumps. This activity is not only a form of entertainment but also serves as a means of relaxation. It provides satisfaction to respondents by enabling them to share and appreciate the memories collected in curated photo and video collections.

Furthermore, for some individuals, this practice enhances their mood, contributing to a brighter day.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I watch their dumps to know what they did this month, as a girl who's always inside her house, it makes me feel nice that they are able to enjoy their lives.”*
- *“Self enjoyment and satisfaction. I just love sharing random things online.”*
- *“Some photos or videos that made me happy. With that, it feels like I'm sharing my happiness with friends/relatives who find it also worth the engagement.”*

Public Service Purposes

While some respondents are actively engaging in student and public service organizations, the utilization of photo/video dumps serves as a medium for their activities to ensure extensive publicity, reaching a broader audience.

Answers from the respondents:

- *To update my constituents on what I do daily as their SK Chairperson.”*
- *“I engage in producing, sharing, and engaging with photo/video dumps, especially for organizational events, to ensure that publications reach a wider audience.”*

Table 13. Participation Influenced Lifestyle.

Participation has influenced their Lifestyle		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
YES	62	62%
NO	38	38%
TOTAL	100	100%

Among the respondents, 62 acknowledged that engaging in photo/video dumps influenced their lifestyle, while 38 see no significant changes despite participating in the activity.

INFLUENCE TO LIFESTYLE

For respondents who responded YES to the previous question, the researcher included a follow up question regarding the effects of participating in photo/video dumps on their lifestyle. This question provided an opportunity for respondents to expound on their agreement. Responses can be classified into the following categories:

Posting as Part of their Lifestyle

Some individuals have adopted the habit of sharing their dumps on a weekly basis. This practice serves as a means to track their weekly activities and monitor

their progress. Notably, at the end or the middle of each month, many engage in compiling 'monthly dump' or 'mid [month] dump'. This involves users sharing a collection of photos and videos showcasing their activities over the course or in the middle of the month. While some individuals opt to post daily, others find satisfaction in establishing a routine, where the content shared is smaller and varied compared to the more detailed weekly, mid-monthly, and monthly compilations.

Answers from the respondents:

- *"I've made it a habit to post monthly or sometimes even weekly dumps. Seeing them all in my personal account and being able to look back at them whenever i want to never fails to warm my heart. It always puts a smile to my face whenever i get to see all the fond memories I've created, especially during times that things aren't going my way"*
- *"It sometimes feels satisfying, like a completed task."*
- *"It has become a part of my routine to send a photo update whenever I'm doing something."*

Memory Making

Creating memories has played a vital role in the lives of the participants since they began sharing photo/video dumps on Instagram. Apart from preserving moments, they ensure to have at least a few photos or videos each month to remember the memories shared with others. Additionally, they enjoy recording life experiences to reminisce later on. This practice also inspires some to seek new adventures and make lasting memories with their loved ones.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“Capturing moments that I think is significant on my life is part of my lifestyle ever since I was kid as my family is into taking pictures. It has influenced me as I grow up. For me, the impact is positive because it has become good personality of mine. Someone that like to take pictures and share them to my friends.”*
- *“Even though college life has been stressful, I get to enjoy life and enjoy the little moments”*
- *“It has impacted my lifestyle because I will not let myself having no pictures or captured memories in a day/month.”*
- *“It enabled me to appreciate how important moments come and go. It encouraged me to keep taking photos and videos to treasure and to look back on when the time comes.”*

Becoming More Interactive with People

Photo/video dumps offer a platform for users to organize and share their photo and video collections with others, fostering interactive engagement in the online community. Some users find that having photo/video dumps creates a safe environment for them to express themselves openly. It also enables them to engage with like-minded individuals, as well as reconnect and keep in touch with people who supported them from the past.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I get to reconnect again with my friends, i only post once in a while so it feels like a life update to my close friends (ppl who have access on my acc). It feels good kapag kinakamusta nila ako and sometimes they even cheer me up. It feels so nice lang knowing na there is someone supporting you grow :))”*

- *“It helps me socialize more”*
- *“Definitely in a positive way. I was happy and contented to be able to share moments of my life every month and to appreciate the people who helped get through every day.”*

Boosting Confidence in a Gentle Way

Photo and video dumps have proven beneficial for participants by offering them a new perspective on life. This activity not only encourages them to participate but also helps in enhancing their self-representation. By sharing content in a humble online community, respondents have found that it boosts their confidence in a subtle manner. Aside from receiving compliments from their peers, some respondents appreciate the modest approach to curating and sharing content, which differs from the typical posting dynamic which focuses more on thinking of other peoples' impressions rather than providing or receiving positive feedback.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“It helped me to stay updated with new trends and updates regarding my contacts and mutuals. It also boosted my confidence as I post photos or videos of myself on various social media platforms such as on Instagram.”*
- *“It boosts my mood, self expression, confidence, and my ability to engage with other people.”*
- *“Somehow, it was a relief for me. It also boosts my confidence.”*

Improvement in Technicalities

Besides providing a safe environment, photo/video dumps have allowed participants to showcase their skills in capturing moments as they unfold. While

some find it easier to curate and share photos and videos, others are keen on practicing photography and videography techniques to enhance the storytelling aspect of their captured memories. Additionally, photo/video dumps have inspired them to brainstorm new content ideas.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I always try to take pictures of good scenery or capture any cute/fun/memorable moment. I sometimes spend hours editing a video.”*
- *“It impacted my lifestyle positively as I need to learn how to capture stuffs in a proper manner so that it would look good on the finish product or the one that I will upload on the said social media application.”*
- *“In the olden days, only people with the right equipment are able to take pictures, make videos, and produce a masterpiece. Mostly, they are not able to showcase it, unless their crafts can be seen on TV, in magazines, posters, etc. But now, with the use of mobile phones, and social media platforms like Instagram, the talent of people in photography/videography will arise, and can now capture and post such memories and art in no time. That discovery of awakening the creative part of you where you will take time to choose the right angle, color, lighting, filters, and effects to make the image more artistic and worth the share.”*

Tracking Life

The researcher found that participants viewed their photo/video collections as a digital diary, documenting their experiences, particularly during their current college years. Even with hectic schedules, those involved in this activity can better understand the events in their lives and relate to other busy college students, fostering empathy and connections.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“Instagram has become a sort of visual journal and it helps connect people with the same interests.”*
- *“ it’s a great way to keep memories alive and it helps us reflect on how we progress every single day. ”*
- *“Positively, because in that simple activity, I can have an online diary or journal, in videos or pictures, of the events that happened in my life. This helps me to have a reminder on the happy and not so happy events that I have experienced which I can look back anytime. And by that, whenever I look back at my past dumps, I can see which things have already changed or improved in my life over the time.”*

Negative Impacts

When discussing the positive effects of engaging in photo/video dumps on participants' lifestyles and the actions they observed upon starting this activity, some respondents also mentioned some challenges they faced during their involvement:

Prolonged Editing and Curating Process

Some participants acknowledged encountering challenges during their editing and curating process. Apart from the increasing confusion when choosing the proper content for their collections, they also expressed concerns about mistakenly sharing the wrong set of photos or videos on Instagram. Additionally, issues arose during the editing process for those utilizing extra applications, with some respondents mentioning that excessive time was spent editing their videos. Moreover, some respondents mentioned instances where they became too focused on capturing the moment rather than savoring it.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“It became a habit to document things that seemed memorable as I was so shy to do it before. Negatively when it comes to the quality of my output, I am scared to post it regardless of the content.”*

Lack of Privacy

In terms of privacy, some respondents acknowledged their concerns. This was particularly noticeable among respondents affiliated with organizations. Despite recognizing the activity's benefits, some encountered privacy issues when engaging with unfamiliar individuals, resulting in a reduced privacy in their posts. Conversely, some respondents addressed these challenges by restricting their content to only be visible to selected mutual connections, thus controlling who can view their photo or video collections.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“However, on the downside, I feel I am becoming less private when I post.”*
- *“They also come with significant risks to privacy.”*

Overconsumption and Oversharing

Taking part in photo/video dumps can have adverse effects on one's lifestyle if the level of participation is not managed effectively. Some participants face difficulties in consuming content, which can be overwhelming. The process of editing, curating, and sharing content may also seem daunting at times. Moreover, there are instances where college responsibilities are neglected as some participants

easily get distracted while participating. Conversely, some participants acknowledge that they tend to share too much in their own photo/video dumps.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“However, on the downside, I feel I am becoming less private when I post.”*
- *“Overconsumption of social media isn’t good. Though it can’t be helped that we want to share moments of our life (and it’s not wrong to do so!) but I think sometimes everyone just needs to pause and live in the moment because at the end of the day our lives are so much different than what it seems online.”*
- *“Worrying about posting or getting caught up in the pressure of posting or if I may be oversharing too much of my life online.”*

Stress and Personal Issues Arise

Some respondents acknowledged that while sharing photo/video dumps on Instagram brings joy and relaxation to both themselves and their mutuals, it can also induce stress from the pressure to participate. Additionally, there are instances where they experience envy towards the activities showcased in the photo/video dumps of their mutuals.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“Can somehow boost Self-esteem, can be a stress reliever but can also cause stress, made me envious but at the same time, it motivated and influenced me to do and achieve my goals in life.”*

Table 14. Participation Influenced Self-Discovery.

Participation has helped in their long-term self-discovery process		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
YES	59	59%
NO	41	41%
TOTAL	100	100%

When assessing the impact of engaging in such activities on their long-term self-discovery journey, 59 respondents acknowledged that the activity facilitated a deeper understanding of themselves, whereas 41 respondents expressed that the activity did not contribute significantly to their self-discovery.

INFLUENCE TO SELF-DISCOVERY

For the respondents who responded YES to the previous question, the researcher included a follow-up question regarding the impact of photo/video dumps on their long-term self-discovery journey. This question provided an opportunity for respondents to further explain their perspective. Their responses can be classified into the following categories:

Appreciating Life

Initially designed for social interaction, social media has evolved into a platform where users not only engage with others but also explore and develop a deeper understanding of themselves. The respondents acknowledged that sharing photo/video dumps facilitated self-discovery by fostering an appreciation for their experiences. By capturing fleeting moments and memories through visual media, individuals could preserve and revisit shared moments, leading to a heightened sense of gratitude for their life's journey—ranging from everyday occurrences to significant milestones achieved while they're still in college.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I have had a visual representation of how much I've grown these past few years through my photo dumps. I was able to remember memories & milestones in my life — and even capturing the most random days. Through it all, it makes you appreciate life more.”*
- *“Sometimes it's my way of life realization. Minsan kasi nakakalimutan ko na i appreciate yung mga bagay lalo na when life gets too overwhelming and posting*

videos/photos is like a rewind and a moment to appreciate yung mga bagay na achieve ko”

- *“It’s a way to look back and to reflect. It also allows us to appreciate how far we’ve come in the context of looking back at the memories we’ve made.”*

Motivation to Self-Improvement and Self Growth

Engaging in the activity has led some participants to recognize a positive impact on their self-improvement journey by delving into their shared photo/video dumps. This exploration serves not to show negative aspects but rather to evaluate personal growth derived from their involvement in various activities reflected in their visual archives. Additionally, individuals acknowledged that this process facilitated self-awareness, enabling a more comprehensive self-assessment. Interacting with peers engaged in the same activity has proven inspirational, with received words of affirmation and compliments further contributing to their motivation and sense of encouragement.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“Creating those little documentations of my day and life made me realize that I’ve changed and I’ve grown my old habits, may it be positive or bad habits, then it helps me to be conscious on my previous actions and helps me to think of ways how to improve my current state.”*
- *“It helped me in a way that I can look back on the past events in my life, which I can assess myself whether I’ve improved or grown, because I can see which things have already change in my life over the time.”*
- *“In a way, I tend to build up self confidence in sharing photos. Having close friends who also like and comment on my posts helps boost my confidence!”*

- *“Because they let me see how much I’ve grown as a person over the years and who are the people who have contributed the greatest to who I am today.”*

Tracking Interests

Another aspect of self-discovery that participants uncovered while engaging in photo/video dumps is the ability to observe how their interests have evolved over time. This includes changes in their activities, learning goals, and even preferences in styles, particularly for those in the creative field. Moreover, they can evaluate what truly resonates with them and what fails to capture their attention.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“It helped me identify my interest from the past such as the activities, interests, and the people I spend time with.”*
- *“I began to see and learn what works for me as well as the things I am deeply interested in.”*
- *“By creating photo/video dumps, I have discovered more of myself. I realized more of the things that I like and dislike. Moreover, I have discovered that I really am just someone who treasures memories so much. Through photo/video dumps, I get to reminisce about the good memories I’ve made with people I love.”*

Being Transparent in the Online World

The apprehension of excessive social media use can lead to an idealized persona both online and offline. Sharing photo/video dumps encourages transparency, allowing audiences to gain a deeper insight into an individual's life events. Feedback from the respondents revealed that this practice helped them be more open online, acknowledging that their online persona aligns with their real-life

self. This positive experience demonstrates the possibility of being authentic and transparent on social media, aiding in self-discovery.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I wouldn’t say that the Posting part is what assisted me in my journey of self-discovery, but rather the process of choosing what photos/videos to include in the post, as well as what to write for my captions. It makes me realize what things or which people I value more than others, and it would drive me to make the conscious effort of being completely genuine or transparent online.”*
- *“It helped get in touch with my creative side without being judged, a place where I can just try and try.”*
- *“It made more mature and became more positive in real life situation.”*

Discovering More About Identity

The researcher found that those who acknowledged the impact on their self-discovery process noted significant changes in their personal identity. Many were surprised by their personal growth and transformations, such as discovering unexpected traits like a masculine side as a woman, enhanced creativity over time, being adventurous, having a deep attachment to memories, and various other aspects of their identity. Moreover, some participants shared that these revelations helped to heal their inner child by prompting them to explore their feelings, interests, current state, and aspirations, fostering a sense of belonging and independence.

Answers from the respondents:

- *“I often change my feed depending on how I feel in certain moments. So everytime I change, I get to know this version of me being a boy”*
- *“It made me realize how I wanted to live, and what kind of lifestyle I do. I can see the progress and changes of myself and my thoughts at that time when I look back to my dumps. I also realized my personality through this and confirmed what others can see at my behavior (introverted, the documenter rather than being documented stuff like that). ”*
- *“I discovered that I can freely share my thoughts and photos to my friends even if we're not talking now for a long period of time due to different priorities.”*
- *“Well, I thought I’m a boring person but then looking back from my dump photos and videos I uploaded I guess I am not 😊. Also, I realized I have the talent at editing 📷”*

Table 15. Online Interview and Observation Invitation.

Participation in Online Interview and Observation		
Answers	Frequency	Percentage
YES	37	37%
NO	63	63%
TOTAL	100	100%

In the final question of the survey, respondents were asked about their willingness to take part in the Online Interview and Observation. Out of 100

participants, 37 agreed to join the next phase, while 63 opted to solely participate in the survey.

Phase Two: Online Interview and Observation Results

INTERVIEW

In the initial stage of the methodology, interviewees are grouped into a maximum of six questions during the interview, depending on their survey answers. The core concepts are mostly centered around these particular questions.

Q1 What were your initial thoughts when you first learned about photo/video dumps?

A Safer Space than Main Accounts

While some may view it as a pointless task, photo/video dumps offer a secure environment for the interviewees to freely express themselves and showcase their thoughts, experiences, and accomplishments to a selected group of people.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Tapos nung naisip ko nung ginawa ko dump ko, like okay doon mo mas okay doon mas comfortable ka i-share kung sino ka. Sa main kasi, more on a facade. Kung sino ‘yung gusto na’tin makita nila.”*

- *“Ano, nung iniisip ko gumawa ng ganon anong point? Parang napaka useless. Then may nangyari tapos dun ko lang naisipan gumawa para mas seclude muna, gusto ko rin mag separate ng mga tao (followers) about sa other social life.”*

A Creative Approach to Preserving Memories

Sharing photo/video dumps has emerged as a fresh trend among Instagram users. This activity allows the interviewees to collectively share their experiences on a schedule of their choice – whether weekly, mid-monthly, or monthly. Additionally, some have found this to be a creative method to showcase their photo and video collections.

Answers from respondents:

- *“I think that we could be creative in taking memories of what is happening on our lives”*
- *“Siguro ever since nalaman ko yung video dumps na yan, it’s a good idea na memory keeper siya...Kasama siya sa schedule ko parang priority ko siya gumawa. Mostly din kasi masaya siya gawin hindi siya nakakapressure kasi uso, pero gusto ko siyang gawin kasi masaya siya pati memory keeper.”*
- *“Siguro ‘yung initial is ang galing. Kasi usually nagd-dump lang ng lahat ng pictures walang involved na template. Interesting siguro initially.”*

Enhanced Convenience in Posting

Some of the interviewees prefer the convenience of this activity as it saves time by allowing them to collect and post all at once. This helps them reminisce about the memories they have made.

Answers from respondents:

- *“My initial thoughts, I guess it would be easier to post kasi...Kapag hindi na busy, pwede ko siya i collate and ipost ng isahan. So I think it's convenient.”*
- *“I find it fun while editing photos/videos. Parang summary ng nangyari sa'yo for the month, nababalikan mo.”*

Time Consuming

Although participating in photo/video dumps may seem overwhelming, it also serves as the first impression that resonates with the interviewees. Some find the activity labor-intensive as it involves recording, editing the content if desired, organizing events chronologically, and eventually sharing the collection. The demand for dumps, especially during specific times of the month, can create pressure for interviewees to share their collections promptly.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Nung una i think sabi ko ‘hala hindi ba to matrabaho?’ I thought kasi nung una kasi i-document ng mga tao everyday. And then they would post it after a week. Pero pwede pala na this month dumps. Akala ko talaga matrabaho siya.”*
- *“Nung first ko po siyang na encounter ang first impression ko sa kanya tedious kasi magc-collect ka magpipicture ka, tas mamimili ka kung aesthetic ba yung magkakasama or parehas ng theme ganon.”*
- *“...Pero may feeling ng pressuring at some point parang hala ang dami ng gumagawa non.”*

Q2 Between sharing photo and video dumps, which do you find more engaging and enjoyable? What makes it stand out for you, or do you find both equally appealing?

Memories in Snapshots

Some of the interviewees lean towards assembling photo dumps, finding it simpler to consolidate events at once. Concerns arose regarding Instagram's time constraints for posting video dumps, unlike the flexibility offered with photo collections. Users can share up to 6 frames in an Instagram story and up to 10 photos in a main post. Additionally, they acknowledged that editing videos can be time-consuming due to the need to learn various video editing techniques.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Siguro more engaging in general ‘yung photos kasi mas marami kang atleast for me malalagay pwede kang mag mix of everything. Sa videos pwede rin naman kaso sa case ko, kasi hindi ako magaling mag edit ng videos.”*

Memories Captured in Motion

Majority of the interviewees revealed a preference for video dumps over photos. They believe that videos make it simpler to relive memories and emotions, even though they may take more time. Similarly, echoing the previous point, some interviewees expressed that editing photos is more demanding than editing videos due to the various techniques involved.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Sa video naman, pinopost ko more on memories, events gala lalo with friends and family. Mas comfy ako i share d'on...ayun mas okay videos kasi nare-reminisce.”*
- *“Siguro video though marami akong pinopost na photo. Pag video kasi, based on my observations ha, mababalikbalikan mo kasi kaysa sa mga pictures. Kasi pag video kasi once na mapanood mo maraming bumabalik na memories sa'yo, marami kang maaalala.”*
- *“Ngayon po kasi sa aking other ig acc more on vid dumps ako nage edit ako about my day, kapag nagkikita kami nila [name mentioned]. Pagdating sa photo hindi masyado or hindi talaga ako nagphoto dump last grad pa po. Hindi ako mahilig mag take ng photos isa pa yun sa iisipin ko parang ano bang maganda angle na 'to, ano bang aesthetically pleasing para sa makakakita. Pati nasaktuhan ko rin 'yung pagkahilig ko sa film.”*

Both are Equally Meaningful Based on Purpose

Some interviewees appreciate both mediums equally. Video dumps allow them the freedom to create compilations with music and transitions they enjoy, while photo dumps serve as cherished memories to reflect upon. Additionally, both mediums can be artistic expressions that offer diverse creative avenues.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Pareho silang engaging sa ibang paraan. 'Pag video kailangan magrecord ng video, kapag natapos mo na pagsasamasamahin mo na 'yun. Kailangan din ng music, cut cut per second. Sa photo dump engaging siya kapag tiningnan mo afterwards mababalikan mo. Kunwari wala kang magagawa p'wede mong balikan.”*

- *“I find both of them appealing because we find art in different ways, like it could be in a form of a picture which upholds a thousand meaning or if in a video it could be in a form of timelapse which show a progressive art for me.”*

Q3 Given that photo/video dumps are originally known for capturing specific or spontaneous moments in an individual's life, often reflecting a particular mood or narrative, do you think this concept still holds true? Or has it evolved into a trend that people simply want to join in on, becoming somewhat idealized in the way instagram users portray themselves to others?

A Trend that Showcases an Idealized Self-image

In the quest for online acceptance, the interviewees noted that photo/video dumps can be perceived as a trend. When social media users portray an idealized version of themselves through these activities, it can create a sense of conformity. However, there are also opportunities for individuals to express themselves in unique and varied ways.

Answers from respondents:

- *“On the other hand, most of the gen z's nowadays have their social media for themselves to portray an idealized self-image encompassing their self-worth and expressing themselves in their own ways.”*
- *“Sa trend siguro may factor yung ganon. Kasi dun mo rin mabubuo ‘yung image mo on how you want people to foresee you ayun po.”*

The Concept Remains

Despite the initial trend-driven adoption of the photo/video dump concept, its essence remains unchanged. Most of the interviewees acknowledged its evolution into a trend, yet the genuine motive behind participating in this activity remains intact. Particularly for early adopters, the practice holds valuable memories. Additionally, the storytelling aspect persists with a select audience, as the primary aim is personal recollection to preserve memories on a dedicated platform.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Pati doon nakikita mo ‘yung true emotions so parang naf-feel mo rin ‘yun. Hindi siya for the trend, atleast for me.”*
- *“Siguro ‘yung concept na yon still holds true pa rin lalo sa mga naunang mag adapt. Ayun nga, it still holds true kasi may particular memory siya sa sarili mo...May iba siguro na nakikiride lang din pero sa’kin after a while, may relevant meaning siya sa’kin.”*
- *“For me for story moments, memories. Sa ig kasi may pili akong people na may dump sila. Like nagd-dump lang talaga sila d’on ng pics and vids. Tapos ano, parang sinitore lang nila na ayun nangyari this month...Like for me story pa rin siya. Parang ‘di ko pa nakikita ‘yung trend talaga siguro din factor din mga finafollow mo.”*
- *“Yung paggawa ko po ng vid dumps is more for my own consumption rather than sa ibang tao kaya para sa’kin po significant pa rin po siya because minsan mo lang ma document, mahirap na siya balikan and obviously hindi mo na mababalikan ‘yung nakaraan. Kaya parang maganda siyang archival dump kumabaga.”*

Q4 How do you feel about incorporating extra applications or software to enhance the mood and credibility of your photo/video collections?

Common Goal, Infused with User Preferences

While some interviewees opted for simpler photo and video tools in their uploads, others preferred vibrant colors or aesthetics that resonated with their personalities. Additionally, some aimed to showcase their creativity through their choices.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Minimal lang ‘yung changes. I do encourage it pero more on Instagram lang ako. Ayan brightness, contrast. Lalo kapag gusto ko magpop-up ‘yung color. Lalo ‘yung background or ‘yung mukha ko, damit ko.”*
- *“Kunwari pictures ganon, kung ano gusto ko ipakita. Like gamit, lalo 70s 80s, need ng software parang kailangan ng specific vibe para d’on.”*
- *“I find it better when I can edit the video or photo according to my liking because it brings me joy that I can be with the same level as the best photographers in the world. Like I'm having my own art instead of just mesmerizing someone's.”*
- *“Kasi diba iniisip ko kasi yung pride ko as a Multimedia Studies student. Tapos ayoko na maglagay ng basta na edit lang. Basta hindi overwhelming yung interface siguro para minimalistic yung dating. Kasi nga gusto ko ng medyo high quality na ipost lalo sa video pero pics okay lang madali lang ‘yung photo.”*

Applications Providing Predefined Settings and Templates

Various applications come equipped with preloaded tools and templates for editing photos and videos, making the editing process easier while preserving an attractive visual result.

Frustrations During the Editing Process

Some interviewees expressed a desire to create a specific mood in their photo/video collections, only to encounter frustration when they couldn't achieve it. This can also be challenging for those who are not comfortable with editing or technical aspects.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Minsan kapag tinatry ko mag edit, tapos kapag hindi ko na r-reach yung goal, hindi ko na siya ineedit. Naiinis lang, nagsayang ako ng time like ipost ko nalang ng walang filter.”*
- *“Una, nakakpressure siya as someone na hindi naman mahilig (mag edit) or techy. ‘Yung CapCut nga ngayon ko lang ginamit. Pero totoo kasi na lalo yung transitions na gusto mo nasa apps siya, kaya kailangan mo rin makisama gan'on. ”*

A Tool to Convey a Mood and Story

Some of the interviewees view the use of additional apps as a way to enrich their storytelling process rather than altering it, aiming to express the emotions and atmosphere they want to share with their viewers. Editing is seen as a pleasurable task by some, allowing them to infuse the captured moments with a personal touch.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Para sa’kin kasi enjoyable process tas ayun nga nae-enhance ‘yung kung anu anong dinodocument ko. I frequently use po extra applications...From how i use po for the video, hindi ko naman siya ineedit in such a way na may maiba. Kung ano lang ‘yung nasa video dun ako nagb-base kung pa’no ako mag-edit.”*
- *“I think depende pa rin sa user, depende sa kung saan ip-post kasi kunwari sa ibang apps. For those people like hindi naman nag-compromise...Feeling ko sa’kin hindi, kahit na malabo yung picture gagawan ko siya ng six template. I think nasa personality ko kasi na funny funny kaya hindi ko siya iniisip. Kaya sakin okay lang pero depende siya sa tao pero for me hindi siya nac-compromise.”*

Q5 As highlighted in the survey, college activities can get quite demanding and hectic which can affect our overall lifestyle. Despite this, what motivates you to continue participating in photo/video dumps?

A Glimpse of Life in College

Most of the interviewees expressed their desire to document their college experiences through photo and video dumps, even with their busy schedules. For many, it serves as a way to cherish memories amidst the challenges and demanding nature of college life. Additionally, it fosters connectivity, enabling them to preserve memories and stay connected with peers. Particularly for distance learners, going out, experiencing, and recording memories energizes them.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Like siguro after monday to friday, magc-collect ako ng pictures photos. Ayun ‘yung naging drive ko para patuloy ‘yung pagp-post ko lagi...Oo parang naging journal sa’kin the past months, past years. Parang gusto ko mag reminisce na ito pala mga nangyari sa’kin,”*
- *“Kasi ‘yung you only live once kaya sulitin mo na...Make sure na nasisiyahan ka pa rin sa araw mo, kasi mahirap na mabuhay ngayon tapos nasasayahan ka na kahit nahihirapan ka...Gusto ko i capture yon and by the end of the month, ah maraming masayang nangyari sa’kin this month kahit na maraming problema and that keeps me going...I’m making positive vibes sa sarili ko at para sa iba.”*
- *“Ano talaga, for storing memories tapos ano, when I’m out. Usually tayo sa OU, usually nasa bahay lang, nasa office... Gusto kong maramdaman ‘yung feeling ulit, nae-energize ako when I’m with people. Like binabalikan ko uli siya, binabrowse ko.”*
- *“Feeling ko kasi kahit ga’no ka hectic ang college of life in general, ‘yung dumps na ‘yan is something na pwede mo balikan... Ako personally appreciative ako sa mga tao lalo kapag may binigay ka sa’kin ip-post ko ‘yan sa ig. Like parang gusto ko i-appreciate ‘yung mga taong ina-appreciate ko through posting dumps like this...in times na malungkot ako nas-stress ako binabalikan ko ‘yung videos, like part siya na nag momotivate sa’kin in general.”*

Archiving Memories

According to the interviewees, their main motivation for participating in photo/video dumps is the desire to preserve memories tailored to their preferences. Moreover, certain memories carry significant sentimental value for the interviewees.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Ayun nga kasi nga ginagawa ko ‘yung video to have something to look back on pati organized person kasi ako e. Kapag nagawa ka ng dumps nao-organize mo ‘yung photos and how you want to post them.”*
- *“Ayun nga po the thought of something na mababalikan especially kung memorable ‘yung moments na ‘yun parang sentimental value siya ganon. Hindi ko rin naman po siya ginagawang habitual like trabaho ko na parang a content creator would. As in kung maisipan ko lang talaga gumawa. ”*

Bringing Passion Into Life

Interviewees who sought to express and nurture their creativity through their work found their engagement to dumps to be a driving force to enhance their abilities, showcase them to a wider audience, and facilitate connections with those in their community.

Answers from respondents:

- *“What motivates me to continue this kind of passion is myself and the people around me who appreciate me and love me even though I don't normally talk to them. Also, I'm motivated to create an album to document my life throughout the end like the places I've been, important events, and many more.”*

Q6 As time passes by, do you find that engaging in these activities helps you discover more about yourself? Are there new things that make you know yourself better when you participate in such activities?

The Authentic Self in the Online Realm

During the interviews, the interviewees acknowledged feeling at ease revealing their true selves when sharing photo or video content, which inspired them to express their authenticity to others.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Yes for me important ang pagd-dump ng photos and videos. Kasi mas nagiging komportable ka to share your true self to others. It’s a way to bridge the gap of insecurity. Ta’s ish-share ko selfies ko sa ppl sa dump ko like it’s a huge step towards self love, self confidence importante ‘yun especially discovering yourself.”*

Boosting Self-Esteem

For the interviewees who deal with insecurities, this activity has proven to be a crucial instrument in enhancing self-confidence. Moreover, it has enabled them to recognize their progress and present themselves confidently to others, supported by their Instagram mutuals who support their self-assurance by reciprocating appreciation both online and offline.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Kaya mas na-discover ko sa sarili ko nung pinost ko yon parang gusto ko pa ‘to gawin, parang nakakagaan ng loob nung ginawa ko ‘yon. Tapos more on mas nagiging okay ako sa sarili ko, more pictures, more selfies, more postings. There are*

things na na-discover ko nga na ayun nga mas naging okay ako sa sarili ko, mas naging 'ah, okay ganito pala dapat ako. Parang mas gusto ko pala na maging ganito ako, mas comfortable ako sa gan'to' yung gan'on. Kaya mas nagp-participate ako sa pag-dump, kasi mas nakakagaan siya sa'kin, tumataas 'yung self-esteem, self-confidence.'"

- *"May insecurities kasi ako beh...Natatakot ako sa engagement na baka kasi walang maka-appreciate sakin. Ngayon syempre alam ko naman na ano, na observe ko naman sa sarili ko na inimprove naman ako...Kaya ayun, nakatulong nga sa'kin yung dump through posting...Kumabaga 'yung dump 'yung naging instrument na maging confident, magkar'on ng self improvement."*
- *"As the years went by, parang nakikita ko na sa picture na 'to pero pinost ko pa rin. Kasi gusto ko makita 'yung evolution ko, also that time hindi ako mahilig magtake ng pics kasi insecure ako most of the time and nasasayangan ako. So parang in a way I get to know myself better."*

Exploring Interests, Preferences, and Styles

Majority of the interviewees reported that they enjoy compiling their photo and video collections as they uncover their preferences throughout the process, starting from recording/capturing, editing, organizing, to sharing/posting. Some acknowledged that they can pinpoint their interests by actively participating in these activities.

Answers from respondents:

- *"Yes it helps me to discover more about myself in terms of pag nac-compile ako ng dumps, yung style ko. For example ako mahilig ako mag-take ng photos ng sunset, nadidiscovers ko 'yung style ko lalo with the photos I like to capture."*

- *“Yes beh oo, until now naman kasi nakikita ko naman na nad-discover ko ‘yung sarili ko through posting. Dito ko kasi nadedevelop ‘yung interests ko sa mga bagay lalo na ngayon... Kasi ano ‘yun e kung eexplore mo yung sarili mo through your dump, makikilala mo kasi ‘yung sarili, anong interest nagf-fit sa sarili mo. ”*
- *“Feeling ko po yes kasi parang through documenting my life parang naf-filter ko na po yung moments that I feel are significant or it’s worthy of being documented. Yes, it’s a way na rin po siya na pag flashback ng aking interests as time goes by kasi napansin ko sa sarili ko na I don’t have something constant na fav ko. I frequently have high expectations as I call it.”*
- *“Parang mas nabubuo ko ‘yung personality ko na gusto ipakita sa iba through choosing the photos na ilalagay ko ayun.”*

A Reminder of Growth

Some of the interviewees track their journey through their photo and video dumps, capturing their accomplishments and significant experiences during college. Digital platforms have evolved into secure spaces, particularly for sharing cherished memories.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Ngayon nasa isip ko, ang layo na pala ng narating ko. Ang dami kong na experience. Andami kong ik-keep along the way. Nakikita ko may ups and downs ako rito, ayun...Recently sa nasugbu sabi ng kaibigan ko comfort is the enemy of growth. Kaya ayun ‘yung naaalala ko rito. ”*

New Personal Discoveries

During the process, the interviewees often discover new aspects of their personalities as they evolve. Moreover, engaging in such activities enables them to meet like-minded individuals who resonate with them.

Answers from respondents:

- *“Siguro naman, engaging naman helps to discover kasi narealize ko na mahilig din naman ako magpicture kahit na hindi naman siya super nice...mag effort pa rin mag pictures kaso more of appreciating ‘yung environment around me, people and things na meron ako...parang nakikita ko yung match and people na ka match ko nung pinopost. Tapos sila gan’on din, nakikilala ko ‘yung medyo same wavelength na nakakatawa rin...That way nakikilala ko rin sarili ko, lalo humor talaga is part ko.”*

OBSERVATION

Applications Used

Most of the interviewees use the following applications to create their own photo/video dumps:

CapCut. As indicated in the survey findings, CapCut emerged as the main tool utilized by most respondents and was also observed during the online phase. This application provides built-in templates and settings to streamline the editing process and enhance visual appeal. Users can also tailor their videos to their liking using this feature.

TikTok. Just like CapCut, TikTok provides similar features but in a faster manner. Besides focusing on user engagement, TikTok also includes in-app payments, which CapCut offers without any fees.

Instagram. Apart from serving as a social media platform, Instagram offers fundamental editing tools for both photo and video content. Some interviewees find Instagram convenient for editing, as it allows them to record, edit, and post seamlessly in one place.

Adobe Creative Suite. For interviewees who value creative results in their photo and video dumps, Adobe Creative Suite, specifically Adobe Photoshop and Adobe Lightroom, is utilized for its flexibility in assisting with their creative needs.

Minimal Editing

While the interviewees are interested in contributing to photo/video dumps, they also prefer methods that streamline the editing process to create visually appealing collections quickly.

Basic Tools

Some of the interviewees prefer not to use presets for organizing the mood of their photo collections. They prefer adjusting the brightness and contrast while preserving the original features of their photos and videos. On the other hand, some opt not to resize their photos and prefer sharing them in their unaltered form. Moreover, some of the interviewees lean towards editing applications that enable them to capture, edit, and share content effortlessly in a single session.

One interviewee highlighted the usefulness of the "Live Photo" feature in iPhone cameras. This feature enables iPhone users to capture a photo and edit it like a video by automatically recording a 1.5-second clip along with the photo.

Built in Templates and Presets

Some of the interviewees opt for built-in templates and presets, enabling users to personalize the template easily by incorporating photos and videos from their galleries.

Photography and Videography Techniques

Some of the interviewees choose to take a more hands-on approach to capturing and editing their photo/video content, rather than relying on the basic tools provided by applications.

Photography Techniques

When gathering photos, some of the interviewees have specific camera angle preferences. In terms of layouts, some of the interviewees favor a 4-framed layout over a 6-framed one to showcase all photos within one frame. Additionally, one interviewee mentioned that using these layouts allows for blending the colors across photos to create a harmonious, color-coordinated frame.

The researcher discovered an interesting photography technique during an interview with an interviewee. This method involves using a magnifying glass while capturing photos. When the magnifying glass is placed in front of the phone camera lens, the resulting photo creates a fisheye effect without the usual dark edges. Instead of the dark borders, the photo displays the original setting where it was taken.

Videography Techniques

When recording videos, most of the interviewees tend to keep their devices in one place while filming in real-time, while others choose to utilize time-lapse techniques.

One interviewee, who is keen on filmmaking, delves into learning and applying color grading in their video editing process. Some focus on creating a

smooth transition in their compilations, while others pay close attention to synchronizing their chosen audio with the video clips, aiming to align the audio with the video's overall context.

At times, interviewees opt to incorporate the original video sound alongside their selected audio to enhance certain moments within the videos. Additionally, some express frustration when dealing with short recorded videos, requiring them to adjust the playback speed for a better outcome.

Personal Preferences

Aside from analyzing the applications and editing techniques employed by the interviewees, the researcher also allowed the interviewees to discuss their individual preferences and discoveries during the online observation stage.

Expressing Self-Representation through the Collection

Some of the interviewees mentioned that they like to include presets influenced by specific styles in their edits, as it reflects their mood. When it comes to color grading, most of the interviewees prefer using vibrant and warm colors in their photo/video dumps because they feel that these colors align with their personalities.

Based on their interests, respondents curate content that reflects what they enjoy, such as content from games, recent series with memorable characters, textured images, memes, and amusing quotes. Additionally, some of the interviewees prefer collecting selfies in their photo and video dumps, while others

infuse their compilations with inner meaning, making them more relatable and meaningful to their followers.

Life is a Film

Some of the interviewees mentioned that, in addition to common interests, they enjoy adding cinematic elements to their content. They feel that capturing memories through photos and videos is similar to storytelling in films. This approach adds a personal touch to their collections.

Pop Culture

During the observation phase, it was surprisingly noted that a significant number of the respondents belong to an age group where Pop Culture holds importance. This is evident in their diverse interests, ranging from popular aesthetic trends like Y2K, Indie, and Cottagecore to music genres that are globally recognized.

Some of the interviewees even expressed admiration for Pop Culture figures in the KPOP realm, including BTS, NCT, and SEVENTEEN, as well as the PPOP industry. Specifically, one interviewee highlighted their affinity for the Philippine Nation's Girl Group BINI by sharing their photo and video dump.

Analysis

The researcher in this section delved into the significance of both quantitative and qualitative findings obtained from surveys, online interviews, and observations. This analysis aligns with addressing the research questions outlined in the Research Problem.

RESEARCH QUESTION 1 | HOW ACTIVE USERS ARE ON INSTAGRAM BASED ON THE AVERAGE SCREEN TIME THEY SPEND ON THE APPLICATION (COMMONLY KNOWN AS APP) EVERY WEEK?

Through a thorough analysis of college Instagram users in Laguna and their active engagement with the app, respondents in the survey provided insights. Table 8 reveals that 5% of participants usually spend 35 hours per week on Instagram, equating to a maximum of 5 hours daily. The majority of respondents, however, spend 1 to 2 hours on the platform each day with a total of 14 hours per week.

Regarding the second research question, a majority of participants mentioned that their level of engagement on Instagram could be described as Occasional.

**RESEARCH QUESTION 2 | HOW OFTEN DO THEY ENGAGE IN POSTING DUMPS
BASED ON THE FREQUENCY OF THEIR POSTS/STORIES ON INSTAGRAM, THE
TYPE OF EVENTS/SCENARIOS IN THE PHOTOS/VIDEOS TAKEN, AND THE
ADDITIONAL APPS THEY USE TO PRODUCE THE PHOTO/VIDEO DUMP?**

When assessing the engagement of college Instagram users in Laguna, the researcher incorporated questions about their posting frequency, the typical events or scenes depicted in their photo or video collections, and the supplementary tools or techniques employed to produce their visual content.

As previously stated in the research question, over half of the participants reported their level of engagement on Instagram as Occasionally, with 52 respondents. Additionally, 22 respondents stated they were engaged Always or Very Frequently, demonstrating a higher level of activity (see Table 9).

In their photo and video collections, most respondents incorporate Random Events, with a total of 76 respondents (see Table 10). Additionally, 69 respondents mentioned Special Events, while Self Expression, Gathering, and Daily Routine were included by 51, 50, and 29 respondents, respectively. Random Events received the highest frequency score among other suggested content, aligning with the purpose behind creating photo/video compilations.

While some respondents choose to utilize additional applications to compile their photo/video collections, a majority of 77 respondents confirmed using extra apps for this purpose (see Table 11). The primary tools preferred by respondents for editing photos and videos are CapCut, followed by Instagram (see Table 12). This

was further confirmed during online observations, wherein the interviewees predominantly used CapCut, with Instagram, TikTok, and Adobe Creative Suite following suit. Upon exploring the use of applications in the context of creating photo/video dumps that typically feature unprocessed and diverse content, it was discovered that these collections can also convey a particular mood or narrative, as revealed in online interviews. Interviewees expressed that the purpose of the collection remains consistent, serving as a means to enhance storytelling based on the user's desired communication style.

The researcher also assessed the interviewees' engagement by examining how they utilized additional applications during online observations. Various methods were presented, each supported by different factors. These methods ranged from minimal editing with basic tools to using preloaded tools and templates for editing photos and videos, resulting in visually appealing outcomes in less time. Techniques like layouting, framing, color coordination, and usage of magnifying glass were categorized under photography methods, while real-time filming, time-lapse, color grading, audio-video synchronization, and playback speed adjustments were classified as video techniques. Additionally, interviewees shared their preferences during the observation, some emphasizing self-representation in the editing and curation process to achieve a cinematic quality. The discussion also touched on pop culture elements.

It was noted that in the survey and online interview and observation, some of the interviewees shared their frustrations about using extra applications while editing and curating. They expressed concerns about content, discomfort or lack of knowledge in editing and technical areas, and difficulty achieving the desired look for

their photo/video collections. Additionally, during online observations, a majority of the interviewees favored video dumps as they evoke strong emotions and offer a more convenient method to relive the memories captured through the lens.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3 | HOW DO CREATING PHOTO/VIDEO DUMPS AFFECT THEIR LIFESTYLE AND SELF-DISCOVERY BASED ON THE PURPOSE OF POSTING PHOTO/VIDEO DUMPS, AND LEVEL OF VALIDATION AND SIGNIFICANCE WHILE ENGAGING IN THE ACTIVITY?

The researcher delved into the effects of creating photo/video dumps on individuals' lifestyles and self-discovery. By investigating the main reasons why respondents share, the study examined how this activity impacts lifestyle and contributes to self-discovery.

When the researcher inquired about the main reasons for respondents' active involvement in photo/video dumps, they mentioned archiving old photo and video collections, sharing life events, clout chasing, online interaction, self-expression, satisfaction and enjoyment, and public service motivations. To delve deeper into these reasons, the researcher explored the initial impressions of the interviewees upon discovering photo/video dumps. It was revealed that this activity provides a secure and creative approach of preserving memories. Additionally, there were perceptions of convenience and time consumption associated with the activity when respondents first encountered it.

Sixty-two respondents recognized that participating in photo/video dumps impacted their lifestyle (see Table 13). The influences include posting weekly, preserving memories, engaging with mutuals, boosting confidence, enhancing photography and videography skills, and documenting life events. In online interviews, respondents expressed similar feelings, highlighting how college life has become intertwined with their lifestyle. They find sharing events from their

universities through photo/video dumps valuable for preserving memories and tracking their college experiences, especially during challenging times. Some respondents found that engaging with their photo and video collections helped them bring their passions to life by incorporating them into their daily routines. It also provided them with opportunities to connect with others. However, there were also challenges reported, including extended editing and curating times, privacy concerns, excessive sharing, overconsumption, as well as stress and personal issues. To address these issues, some suggested a thorough curation process and being selective about who can view their photo and video collections.

On the contrary, 59 survey respondents acknowledged that engaging in photo/video sharing has had a significant impact on their journey of self-discovery. Apart from gaining a deeper appreciation for their lives and uncovering more about their identity, the key themes that emerged during the interviews included self-improvement, personal growth, exploring interests, and being authentic even in the online sphere. The interviewees expressed similar views, recognizing that sharing photo/video content facilitated their ability to be genuine online and transparent with their peers, particularly those who provided a supportive environment. Additionally, sharing photo/video content contributed to boosting self-confidence and reflecting on their progress through their dumps, while also enabling them to delve into their interests, preferences, and style, and embrace new discoveries openly. A crucial insight gathered from the interviews was that sharing photo/video content helped individuals overcome their insecurities and further explore their identity.

To further explore how photo/video dumps impact respondents' lifestyle and self-discovery, the researcher conducted online interviews and observations. The interviewees were questioned about whether photo/video dumps still maintain their original purpose of capturing specific or spontaneous moments that reflect personal emotions or stories, or if they have transformed into a trend showcasing an idealized self-image. Interviewees noted that while some users engage in the trend to follow the crowd, others see it as an opportunity to express themselves uniquely. Despite its evolution into a trend, the interviewees agreed that the core concept of photo/video dumps still remains, especially among early adopters. Moreover, storytelling remains a key element for a specific audience, with the primary goal being personal reminiscence, exploration, and self-expression to preserve memories on a dedicated platform.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary and Conclusions

The objective of this study was to explore the impact of photo/video dumps on the lifestyle of college students in Laguna on Instagram, and how this engagement influences their self-discovery. Using a mixed methods approach, specifically the Convergent Parallel Design, the researcher gathered data from 100 respondents using Google Forms. Additionally, 10 respondents agreed to take part in the subsequent phase of the study, which includes Online Interviews and Observations. The majority of the respondents sharing photo/video dumps are between the ages of 21-25 and are predominantly Fourth Year college students pursuing Bachelor of Science degrees. Furthermore, many of these students mainly reside in Calamba, Laguna.

When assessing the level of engagement of college Instagram users in Laguna with the app, it was discovered that they typically spend 1-2 hours per day or 14 hours per week on the platform. Their interaction with photo/video dumps is described as occasional. The data revealed that Random Events received the highest frequency score among the content shared, aligning with the purpose of creating these compilations. Most users do not perceive the use of additional applications as compromising the rawness and authenticity of these compilations. Instead, users maintain consistency in their collections to enhance storytelling based on their preferences. Furthermore, CapCut has emerged as the preferred platform for creating and editing these collections, offering templates and settings to

streamline editing and improve visual appeal, allowing users to customize their videos to suit their preferences.

Various approaches have been identified in using additional apps for organizing photo and video collections, ranging from basic editing to diverse photography and videography techniques. Personal preferences play a key role in curating these collections, with an unexpected incorporation of Pop Culture, tailored to the preferences of college Instagram users in Laguna. Moreover, it was discovered that video compilations are preferred over photo compilations as they evoke intense emotions and provide a convenient way to revisit captured memories.

The study revealed that engagement with photo/video dumps can impact the lifestyles of college Instagram users in Laguna. These influences encompass posting regularly, cherishing memories, interacting with peers, boosting confidence, improving photography and videography skills, and documenting life events. Notably, these influences revolve around their college experiences, sharing university events through photo/video dumps to preserve memories and track their journey, especially during tough times. Moreover, active participation by college Instagram users in Laguna directly contributes to their self-discovery. Beyond developing a deeper gratitude for their lives and exploring their identity, key themes include self-improvement, personal growth, pursuing interests, and maintaining authenticity in the online realm. It was acknowledged that sharing photo/video dumps allow the users to become authentic and transparent online while also connecting with other people. It also enabled users to explore their preferences, interests, and style openly, embracing new discoveries and overcoming insecurities to gain a better understanding of themselves.

Ultimately, it is widely accepted that photo/video dumps have transformed into a trend while preserving their initial intent. Some individuals participate in this trend to join the crowd, while others view it as a chance to showcase their uniqueness. Even as it has become a trend, it was acknowledged that the fundamental idea of photo/video dumps remains, playing a crucial role for a specific audience, aiming at personal reflection, discovery, and self-expression to immortalize memories on a designated platform.

Recommendations

Based on the findings discussed earlier, the researcher suggests the following recommendations. During the methodology phase, various challenges were faced, with one major hurdle being the restriction of surveying solely in Laguna. When the survey invitations were shared in social media, numerous potential participants, expressing their interest in participating in the study, met the criteria outlined by the researcher and were identified, although they were not located in Laguna. To address this, it is advised to broaden the study's scope to encompass a larger region. This approach will not only facilitate reaching the target population efficiently but also enable the exploration of diverse perspectives, particularly from surrounding cities and provinces within the Greater Manila Area.

The researcher also suggests that active Instagram users in Laguna, especially those who enhance their photo and video collections with additional applications, should explore more user-friendly apps when aiming to achieve a specific desired mood. Alongside utilizing built-in presets and templates, the

researcher also advises creating mood boards to visually outline personal preferences. This approach facilitates an enjoyable editing and curation experience rather than a frustrating and challenging one. Recommended applications for assistance include Pinterest and Canva.

Additionally, since the researcher noted that a majority of interviewees in the Online Interview and Observation favored video dumps over photo dumps, it would be beneficial for upcoming researchers to explore video dumps further and develop more relevant literature on the subject. This approach will help in better understanding users' preferences when documenting their memories and gaining self-awareness through dynamic visual trackers.

In conclusion, some participants in the study experienced negative effects on their lifestyle due to their online engagement. To address this, the researcher recommends limiting the audience who can view their photo and video collections on Instagram. In addition to selecting appropriate content, Instagram provides various options for limiting viewership without the need to unfollow mutual connections. The platform's "Close Friends" feature, available for both Stories and Posts, enables users to create a list of specific individuals with whom they wish to share their photo/video dumps. While active engagement in this activity is enjoyable, it is equally important to prioritize users' privacy and well-being.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Austria-Cruz, M. C. A. (2019). *Academic Stress and coping Strategies of Filipino College Students in private and public universities in Central Luzon*. <https://ijaems.com/detail/academic-stress-and-coping-strategies-of-filipino-college-students-in-private-and-public-universities-in-central-luzon/>
- Balba, J. C., & Cainigcoy, M. E. (2021). Self-Concept of College Students: Empirical Evidence from an Asian Setting. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 24, 26–37. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v24i1.4784>
- Bailey, E. R., Matz, S. C., Youyou, W., & Iyengar, S. S. (2020). Authentic self-expression on social media is associated with greater subjective well-being. *Nature Communications*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18539-w>
- Blackwell, B. M. (2017). *"To Share or Not to Share: A Study of an Individual's Self-Representation on Instagram in Accordance with Impression Management Theory*. East Tennessee State University. Electronic Theses and Dissertations. Paper 3257. <https://dc.etsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4684&context=etd>
- Costello, S. (2020, December 26). *Everything you need to know about iPhone live photos*. Lifewire. <https://www.lifewire.com/iphone-live-photos-1999618>
- Demeku, A. (2023, April 13). *Photo dumps: What they are and how to start posting them | later.* Retrieved from <https://later.com/blog/instagram-photo-dump-trend/>

Dixon, S.J. (2023, August 31). *Number of worldwide social media users 2023, by region*. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/454772/number-social-media-user-worldwide-region/>

Eares. (2023, July 31). *What health problems do college students usually face?* INQUIRER.net. Retrieved from <https://cebudailynews.inquirer.net/519399/what-health-problems-do-college-students-usually-face>

Fan, X., Deng, N., Dong, X., Lin, Y., & Wang, J. (2019). Do others' self-presentation on social media influence individuals' subjective well-being? A moderated mediation model. *Telematics and Informatics*, 41, 86-102. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2019.04.001>

Gerrard, Y. (2023). *Why are 'photo dumps' so popular? A digital communications expert explains*. Retrieved from <https://canadianinquirer.net/2023/08/21/why-are-photo-dumps-so-popular-a-digital-communications-expert-explains/>

Harris, E., & Bardey, A. C. (2019). *Do Instagram Profiles Accurately Portray Personality? An Investigation Into Idealized Online Self-Presentation*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 871. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00871>

Herman, J., Morin, D., Garnett, C., & Katai, R. (2020). *Instagram Carousel Study*. Socialinsider. Retrieved from <https://www.socialinsider.io/data-geeks/Instagram-Carousel-Study.pdf>

Jean, Abby "Casual Instagram: Video AB" – Atrium. (2022). Retrieved from <https://edspace.american.edu/atrium/portfolio-item/1158/>

Kameke, L.V. (2023, August 22). *SEA: top social media platforms by traffic share and country 2023* | Statista. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1293253/sea-top-social-media-platforms-by-traffic-share-and-country/>

Kemp, S. (2023). *Facebook users, stats, data, trends, and more — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights*. Retrieved from <https://datareportal.com/essential-facebook-stats>

Kemp, S. (2023b). *Instagram users, stats, data, trends, and more — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights*. Retrieved from <https://datareportal.com/essential-instagram-stats>

Kennedy, M. (2022, December 2). *Magnifying glass photography: A quick guide*. Digital Photography School. Retrieved from <https://digital-photography-school.com/create-artistic-photos-magnifying-glass/>

MacFarlane, R. (2023). *Photo dump meaning: Inside the trend dominating Instagram*. Retrieved from <https://sociality.io/blog/photo-dump-meaning/#1-why-are-photo-dumps-so-popular-on-instagram->

New York Times. (2022). The Mundane Thrill of 'Romanticizing Your Life.'
<https://www.nytimes.com/2022/05/11/well/mind/romanticize-your-life-tiktok.html>

OOSGA. (2023). *Social Media in Philippines - 2023 Stats & Platform Trends*. Retrieved from <https://oosga.com/social-media/phl/#:~:text=Generally%2C%20Facebook%20is%20the%20more,actively%20used%20in%20other%20countries>

Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA]. (2021). *Highlights of the Region IV-A (CALABARZON) Population 2020 Census of Population and Housing (2020 CPH)*. Philippine Statistics Authority. Retrieved from [https://psa.gov.ph/content/highlights-region-iv-calabarzon-population-2020-census-opulation-and-housing-2020-cph#:~:text=The%20population%20of%20Region%20IV,and%20Housing%20\(2020%20CPH\)](https://psa.gov.ph/content/highlights-region-iv-calabarzon-population-2020-census-opulation-and-housing-2020-cph#:~:text=The%20population%20of%20Region%20IV,and%20Housing%20(2020%20CPH).).

Schlosser, A. E. (2020). Self-disclosure versus self-presentation on social media. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 31, 1-6. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2019.06.025>

Vincenty, S. (2022, October 4). *'Romanticizing your life' can have real mental health benefits*. Retrieved from <https://www.self.com/story/romanticize-your-life-benefits>

Wong, A., Ho, S., Olusanya, O., Antonini, M. V., & Lyness, D. (2020). The use of social media and online communications in times of pandemic COVID-19. *The Journal of the Intensive Care Society/Journal of the Intensive Care Society*, 22(3), 255–260. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/1751143720966280>

ANNEXES

ANNEX A

Research Instrument

The researcher gathered information through conducting an open-ended survey, and online interviews and observations. The presentation in the research problem served as a reference for both data gathering procedures. The instruments that were used are the following:

- Google Forms for conducting the open-ended survey.

Figure 3. Survey via Google Forms.

The image shows a screenshot of a Google Form. At the top, there is a header image with the text "FALL IN LOVE WITH LIFE" in yellow. Below the header, the title of the survey is displayed in a large, bold, black font: "Captured Fragments of Life: Analyzing the Implications of Creating Photo and/or Video Dumps on College Instagram Users' Lifestyle and Self-discovery in Laguna". Below the title, there is a greeting: "Greetings!". The main body of the form contains a paragraph of text: "Hello, I am Krystalle Aguilar, a senior student from the University of the Philippines Open University. I am conducting a survey for my undergraduate thesis in MMS 200 (Special Project) titled 'Captured Fragments of Life: Analyzing the Effects of Creating Photo and/or Video Dumps on the Lifestyle and Self-discovery of College Instagram Users in Laguna.' This study aims to investigate the impact of creating photo and video dumps on the lifestyle of college students on Instagram and how this activity influences their self-discovery. The survey will only take between 7-10 minutes to complete." Below this paragraph, there is another paragraph: "The researcher acknowledges the obligations outlined in Republic Act No. 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012, concerning the handling of respondents' data. This includes data management tasks such as collection, recording, organization, updating, utilization, consolidation, and disposal. All data gathered from this form will be securely stored within an authorized system, accessible exclusively by the researcher. Additionally, the information collected and stored in this form will be used solely for data collection and analysis purposes." At the bottom of the form, there is a reassurance: "Rest assured that all the information outputs will be handled with utmost confidentiality." and a contact email: "kcaguilar3@up.edu.ph" with a "Switch account" link and a small icon.

Life: Analyzing the Effects of Creating Photo and/or Video Dumps on the Lifestyle and Self-discovery of College Instagram Users in Laguna. This study aims to investigate the impact of creating photo and video dumps on the lifestyle of college students on Instagram and how this activity influences their self-discovery. The survey will only take between 7-10 minutes to complete.

The researcher acknowledges the obligations outlined in Republic Act No. 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012, concerning the handling of respondents' data. This includes data management tasks such as collection, recording, organization, updating, utilization, consolidation, and disposal. All data gathered from this form will be securely stored within an authorized system, accessible exclusively by the researcher. Additionally, the information collected and stored in this form will be used solely for data collection and analysis purposes.

Rest assured that all the information outputs will be handled with utmost confidentiality.

Email *

Valid email

This form is collecting emails. [Change settings](#)

I'm willing to participate in this research study *

I agree

I don't agree

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 5

Demographics

Description (optional)

Email *

Short answer text

Name (SURNAME, First Name) *

Short answer text

Age *

Short answer text

Preferred Gender Pronoun

He/Him

She/Her

They/Them

Prefer not to say

Other...

Year Standing and Course *

(example: III - BA Political Science)

Short answer text

City/Municipality in Laguna *

(example: Calamba, Cabuyao, San Pedro, etc.)

Short answer text

How often do you use Instagram?

(You can check your Digital Wellbeing settings for an exact time or simply estimate how long you spend on the app.)

(example: 1hr and 5 mins a day, approximately 30 minutes, etc.)

Sample Image from Krystalle Aguilar

Short answer text

As someone who participates in creating photo/video dumps, how frequently do you create and post your own photo/video collections on Instagram?

- Always
- Very Frequently
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Very Rarely
- Never

What types of content do you usually collect or post?

(choose as many as you can, you may also answer others if you would like to indicate other content that you usually share)

- Gathering
- Daily Routine
- Random Events
- Special Events
- Self expression
- Other...

Do you utilize additional apps in producing photo/video dumps?

- Yes
- No

If **yes**, which among the app/s are you currently utilizing?

(Select as many as you can, you may also answer others if you would like to indicate other app/s that you usually use)

- Instagram
- TikTok
- CapCut
- Adobe Creative Suite (Premiere, Lightroom, Photoshop, etc.)
- Other...

After section 3 Continue to next section

Photo and Video Dumps: Their Impact on Lifestyle and Self-discovery

Description (optional)

What are the primary reasons for your engagement in producing, sharing, and engaging with photo/video dumps?

Long answer text

Despite the academic and non-academic demands of college life, do you believe that participating in such activities has influenced your lifestyle?

- Yes
- No

*

If so, kindly describe briefly how it has impacted your lifestyle, whether positively or negatively.

(Write N/A if your answered No to the previous question)

Long answer text

*

Does actively engaging in creating photo or video dumps help with your long-term self-discovery process?

Yes

No

*

If so, kindly briefly describe how this experience assisted you in self-discovery during the activity.

(Write N/A if your answered No to the previous question)

Long answer text

*

Would you like to take part in the *Online Interviews and Observations*?

Yes

No

THANK YOU!

Description (optional)

As a token of appreciation, feel free to specify your preferred mode of communication for a chance to win 500 pesos worth of GCash. Apart from that, I wish you happy and well. Remember to appreciate and seize all the wonderful things that life has in store for you!

Thank you for taking part in my research study!

Preferred Mode of Communication

- Email
- Social Media
- Phone
- Other...

If you selected Social Media in the previous question, kindly specify your preferred social media platform and username.

(example: Instagram - ktalleism)

Short answer text

GCash Number

- Canva to design a publicity survey invitation poster.

Figures 4.1 - 4.3. Call for Respondents Pub in Specific Formats made in Canva.

4.1

4.2

4.3

- Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Discord, and X (previously known as Twitter) to reach a broader audience.

Figures 5.1 - 5.4. Call for Respondents Posting on Instagram Story, Facebook, X, and Discord.

5.1

5.2

5.3

5.4

- Certification Document from TCPS 2: Course on Research Ethics, to fulfill the research ethics prerequisite before starting interviews and observations.

Figure 6. TCPS 2 Certification obtained by the Researcher.

- A cover letter and consent form written by the researcher and approved by the chosen respondents for the online observation.

Figure 7. Cover Letter.

COVER LETTER

April __, 2024

Name:

Occupation:

Address:

Dear Ms./Mr./Mx.:

You have been invited to take part in a research project titled "Captured Fragments of Life: Analyzing the Implications of Creating Photo and/or Video Dumps on College Instagram Users' Lifestyle and Self-discovery in Laguna." This study is currently being carried out by Krystalle Aguilar, one of the students from the University of the Philippines Open University enrolled in MMS 200 – Special Project. The purpose of the study is to understand how creating photo and video dumps affect the lifestyle of college students on Instagram, and how this type of engagement impacts their self-discovery.

The online interview and observation process will include:

Interview

The interview will focus on participants' experiences with exploring photo and video collections, their preferences for capturing images or videos, their approaches to engaging in the activity, their views on using supplementary apps, the impact of the activity on their lifestyle, and self-discovery. The number of interview questions will be determined by the survey responses, with a maximum of six questions.

Observation (this is only relevant for participants who utilize other apps for storing photo and video collections)

During the online observation, the researcher will request the participant to demonstrate how they create photo/video dumps by sharing their screen. This interaction allows the researcher to gain valuable insights into the participant's thought process, organization skills, and creativity when it comes to curating photo or video dumps. The participant can either create a collection in real-time or opt to present an existing one while explaining their process of curating the

collection before sharing it. Ultimately, this approach fosters a more comprehensive and insightful exploration of the participant's techniques and the underlying motivations driving their curation process.

Individual responses are collected and documented anonymously while maintaining strict confidentiality. Collective data will be used to show averages or general trends of the responses as a whole. All data will be securely stored in a location only accessible to the researcher.

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You are free to choose not to participate. Should you choose to participate, you can withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind. To enhance the safety of your involvement, the researcher has completed the TCPS 2: Course on Research Ethics to meet the research ethics requirement before commencing interviews and observations. You can view the researcher's certification document [here](#).

If you have questions or concerns during the time of your participation in this study, or after its completion or you would like to receive a copy of the final collective results of this study, please contact: kraguilar3@up.edu.ph or 09298247057.

Respectfully yours,

Aguilar, Krystalle Genese C.

Researcher

ANNEX B

Survey Questions

SECTION 1

Greetings!

Hello, I am Krystalle Aguilar, a senior student at the University of the Philippines Open University. I am conducting a survey for my undergraduate thesis in MMS 200 (Special Project) titled "Captured Fragments of Life: Analyzing the Effects of Creating Photo and/or Video Dumps on the Lifestyle and Self-discovery of College Instagram Users in Laguna." This study aims to investigate the impact of creating photo and video dumps on the lifestyle of college students on Instagram and how this activity influences their self-discovery. The survey will only take between 7-10 minutes to complete.

The researcher acknowledges the obligations outlined in Republic Act No. 10173, the Data Privacy Act of 2012, concerning the handling of respondents' data. This includes data management tasks such as collection, recording, organization, updating, utilization, consolidation, and disposal. All data gathered from this form will be securely stored within an authorized system, accessible exclusively by the researcher. Additionally, the information collected and stored in this form will be used solely for data collection and analysis purposes.

Rest assured that all the information outputs will be handled with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you so much for your patience and time.

- Email
- Name (SURNAME, First Name) (Optional)
- Age
- Preferred Gender Pronoun
- College Year Standing and Course
- Residence In Laguna

SECTION 2

- How often do you use Instagram? (You can check your Digital Wellbeing settings for an exact time or simply estimate how long you spend on the app.)
- As someone who participates in creating photo/video dumps, how frequently do you create and post your own photo and/or video collections on Instagram?
 - Always
 - Very Frequently
 - Occasionally
 - Rarely
 - Very Rarely
 - Never

- What types of content do you usually collect or post? (choose as many as you can, you may also answer *others* if you would like to indicate other content that you usually share)
 - Gatherings
 - Daily routine
 - Random Events
 - Special events
 - Self expression
 - Others:
- Do you utilize additional apps in producing photo and/or video dumps?
 - Yes
 - No
- If yes, which app or apps are you currently utilizing? (Select as many as you can, you may also answer *others* if you would like to indicate other app/s that you usually use)
 - Instagram
 - TikTok
 - CapCut
 - Adobe Creative Suite (Premiere, Lightroom, Photoshop, etc.)
 - Others

SECTION 3

- What are the primary reasons for your engagement in producing, sharing, and engaging with photo and video dumps?
- Despite the academic and non-academic demands of college life, do you believe that participating in such activities has influenced your lifestyle?
 - Yes
 - No
- If so, kindly describe briefly how it has impacted your lifestyle, whether positively or negatively.
- Does actively engaging in creating photo or video dumps help with your long-term self-discovery process?
- If so, kindly briefly describe how this experience assisted you in self-discovery during the activity.
- Would you like to take part in the *Online Interviews and Observations*?
 - Yes
 - No

ANNEX C

Cover Letter and Consent Form (Online Interview and Observation)

COVER LETTER

[Month]__, 2024

Dear Ms./Mr./Mx.:

You have been invited to take part in a research project titled "*Captured Fragments of Life: Analyzing the Implications of Creating Photo and/or Video Dumps on College Instagram Users' Lifestyle and Self-discovery in Laguna.*" This study is currently being carried out by Krystalle Aguilar, one of the students from the University of the Philippines Open University enrolled in MMS 200 – Special Project. The purpose of the study is to understand how creating photo and video dumps affect the lifestyle of college students on Instagram, and how this type of engagement impacts their self-discovery.

The online interview and observation process will include:

Interview

The interview will focus on participants' experiences with exploring photo and video collections, their preferences for capturing images or videos, their approaches to engaging in the activity, their views on using supplementary apps, the impact of the activity on their lifestyle, and self-discovery. The number of interview questions will be determined by the survey responses, with a maximum of six questions.

Observation (this is only relevant for participants who utilize other apps for storing photo and video collections)

During the online observation, the researcher will request the participant to demonstrate how they create photo/video dumps by sharing their screen. This interaction allows the

researcher to gain valuable insights into the participant's thought process, organization skills, and creativity when it comes to curating photo or video dumps. The participant can either create a collection in real-time or opt to present an existing one while explaining their process of curating the collection before sharing it. Ultimately, this approach fosters a more comprehensive and insightful exploration of the participant's techniques and the underlying motivations driving their curation process.

Individual responses are collected and documented anonymously while maintaining strict confidentiality. Collective data will be used to show averages or general trends of the responses as a whole. All data will be securely stored in a location only accessible to the researcher.

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You are free to choose not to participate. Should you choose to participate, you can withdraw at any time without consequences of any kind. To enhance the safety of your involvement, the researcher has completed the **TCPS 2: Course on Research Ethics** to meet the research ethics requirement before commencing interviews and observations. You can view the researcher's certification document [here](#).

If you have questions or concerns during the time of your participation in this study, or after its completion or you would like to receive a copy of the final collective results of this study, please contact: kcaguilar3@up.edu.ph or [REDACTED] 67.

Respectfully yours,

Aguilar, Krystalle Gennise C.

Researcher

CONSENT FORM

- I have read this cover letter and I understand what is being requested of me as a participant in this research study.
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions and all my questions have been answered satisfactorily.
- I understand that participating in this project will involve:
 1. *attending an online interview and observation*
 2. *my voice being recorded*
 3. *photographs / video being taken of me*
 4. *sharing a few photographs / videos taken by me*
- I consent to having my voice recorded / a video taken / photographs taken during this research study.
- I understand that the researcher will be able to identify me but that all information I give will be coded, kept confidential and will be accessed only by the researcher.
- I am aware that the information collected will be stored and will be destroyed once the research has been completed.
- I understand that I will not be identified in any of the results of this research.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the research at any time without penalty.

I freely agree to participate in this research.

Name and Signature of Participant

Date

ANNEX D

Online Interview and Observation Questions

Hello [Name]! Thank you for taking part in the Online Interview and Observation today. Here are some important points to remember before we start:

- There are no correct or incorrect answers during the interview and observation.
- You can respond in Filipino if that's more comfortable for you.
- Feel free to express any concerns you may have during the process, especially if something is troubling you.

You can choose to start with interviews focusing on the impact of photo/video dumps on college Instagram users or observations involving authorized sharing of photos or videos demonstrating dump creation.

OBSERVATION

Throughout the online observations, I will allow you to share your screen as you carry out the activity. Feel comfortable to speak while you compile your photo/video collection. There are no strict rules to follow; create your photo/video dump in any way you like.

INTERVIEW

- What were your initial thoughts when you first learned about photo/video dumps?
- Between sharing photo and video dumps, which do you find more engaging and enjoyable? What makes it stand out for you, or do you find both equally appealing?
- Given that photo/video dumps are originally known for capturing specific or spontaneous moments in an individual's life, often reflecting a particular mood or narrative, do you think this concept still holds true? Or has it evolved into a trend that people simply want to join in on, becoming somewhat idealized in the way Instagram users portray themselves to others?
- How do you feel about incorporating extra applications or software to enhance the mood and credibility of your photo/video collections?
- As highlighted in the survey, college activities can get quite demanding and hectic which can affect our overall lifestyle. Despite this, what motivates you to continue participating in photo/video dumps?
- As time passes by, do you find that engaging in these activities helps you discover more about yourself? Are there new things that make you know yourself better when you participate in such activities?

ANNEX E

Online Interview and Observation Slides

Figure 9.0. Study Title Slide.

Figure 9.1. Disposition Check Slide.

Figure 9.2. Short Background Slide.

Figure 9. 3. Online Interview and Observation Guidelines Slide.

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Reminders:

- There are no correct or incorrect answers during the interview and observation.
- You can respond in Filipino if that's more comfortable for you.
- Feel free to express any concerns you may have during the process, especially if something is troubling you.

Figure 9.4. Observation and Interview Button.

● ● ●

Choose the 1st Activity

OBSERVATION

INTERVIEW

Figure 9.5. Observation Slide with 'Interview' button.

Figure 9.6 Initial Thoughts on Photo/Video Dumping.

Figure 9.7 Preferences in Photo and/or Video Dump.

Figure 9.8 Validity of Photo Dumping Concept.

Figure 9.9 Thoughts on Using Additional Applications.

Figure 9.10 Primary Motivation for Participating in Photo/Video Dumps.

Figure 9.11 Self-discovery Insights for Participating in Photo/Video Dumps.

Question 6

As time passes by, do you find that engaging in these activities helps you discover more about yourself? Are there new things that make you know yourself better when you participate in such activities?

PROCEED TO OBSERVATION

Figure 9.12 Ending slide with contact details.

Thank you!

 kcaguilar3@up.edu.ph

